

The graphic features a central orange circle with a white flower-like pattern. This is surrounded by three smaller circles (blue, green, and green) connected by curved lines. The entire graphic is set against a background of large, faint, overlapping circles in light blue, light green, and yellow, with a magnifying glass icon in the top right.

ODECO

Towards a sustainable Open Data ECOsystem

D5.3

Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

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Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EDP	European Data Portal
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable Principles
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
NG	non-government
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NPO	Non-Profit Organisation
OD	Open Data
ODE	Open Data Ecosystem
ODP	Open Data Platform
ODI	Open Data Infrastructure
OGD	Open Government Data
WP	Work Package

Nr	Partner	Partner short name	Country
Beneficiary			
1	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	Netherlands
2	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	KUL	Belgium
3	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	France
4	Universidad de Zaragoza	UNIZAR	Spain
5	Panepistimio Aigaiou	UAEGEAN	Greece
6	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	Denmark
7	Università degli Studi di Camerino	UNICAM	Italy
8	Farosnet S.A.	FAROSNET S.A.	Greece
Partner organisations			
1	7eData	7EDATA	Spain
2	Digitaal Vlaanderen	DV	Belgium
3	City of Copenhagen	COP	Denmark
4	City of Rotterdam	RDAM	Netherlands
5	CoC Playful Minds	CoC	Denmark
6	Derilinx	DERI	Ireland
7	ESRI	ESRI	Netherlands
8	Maggioli S.p.A	MAG	Italy
9	National Centre of Geographic Information	CNIG	Spain
10	Open Knowledge Belgium	OKB	Belgium
11	SWECO	SWECO	Netherlands
12	The government lab	GLAB	United States of America
13	Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure	ADSI	Denmark
14	GFOSS Open Technologies Alliance	GFOSS	Greece
15	Inno3 Consulting	IC	France
16	Regione Marche	RM	Italy
17	Open Data Institute	ODI	United Kingdom

Executive summary

This deliverable aims at developing an overarching sustainable framework and strategy by addressing the key challenges faced by current open data systems, which are supplier-driven, linear, exclusive, and effort-based, limiting their ability to create sustainable and value-generating Open Data Ecosystems (ODEs).

The main objective of this deliverable was to design an overarching sustainable ODE framework and to propose strategies to pave the way towards a user driven, circular, inclusive, and skill-based Open Data Ecosystem (ODE). To achieve such an overarching sustainable framework and strategies, previous research done in this project has been utilized from different perspectives, such as for bridging the open data supply and demand, for incorporating the different aspects required for ensuring circularity, and for integrating requirements key to ensuring inclusiveness. Building on the work of Van Loenen et al. (2021) and further developing the whole ODECO project based on this work, the deliverable proposes a transformative vision for open data systems by incorporating the ODE drivers, namely user driven, inclusive, circular, and skill-based, towards sustainable and value-creating ODEs. The goal is to move away from fragmented, government-centric open data systems toward ecosystems that maximize value for all stakeholders—government, NGOs, researchers, businesses, and citizens alike—while ensuring fair value distribution and fostering innovation.

The deliverable introduces a comprehensive ODE Framework that integrates components such as stakeholder groups, data provision and usage, driving forces, governance, open data infrastructure, and enabling environments. By utilizing the ODE framework components, we have illustrated their interactions, portraying the complexity of an ODE.

We also identified 83 strategies to further ODE development. Further synthesis gives 29 distinct strategies. This resulted in eleven recommendations for institutions and actors producing, using or otherwise contributing to the ODE, to be implemented in order to support sustainable ODEs. These 11 recommendations may improve usability and accessibility, quality, and participation through a set of 5 technical and 6 governance strategies.

In conclusion, achieving a sustainable ODE requires a multifaceted approach that balances inclusivity, circularity, user driven engagement, and skill-based empowerment. This deliverable represents a step forward in the evolution of ODEs. By addressing the gaps in current systems and leveraging the proposed strategies, the framework and strategies outlined in this study pave the way for a more inclusive, equitable, and innovative open data future. Ultimately, this work contributes to the broader goal of harnessing open data as a powerful tool for societal and economic transformation.

1 Introduction

Numerous studies have examined the concepts of open data and how building open data ecosystems (ODE) can thrive open data initiatives. The motivation behind each study differs with respect to the ODEs elements. In a collective paper, the consortium has explained the underlining causes that hinders ODEs to achieve sustainability and value creation (see Van Loenen et al., 2021). It was identified that current open data systems are supplier-driven, exclusive, linear, and effort-based (Van Loenen et al., 2021). Transforming current open data systems to user driven, inclusive, circular, and skill-based can drive the way towards value-creating and sustainable ODEs¹.

1.1 Objectives

The objective of this deliverable is to develop an overarching sustainable framework/strategy to arrive at a user driven, circular, inclusive, and skill based ODE. It integrates ODECO Work Packages (WP) WP2, WP3, WP4, T5.1 and T5.2 results, and builds further on the results from the individual research projects of the fifteen Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: ODECO deliverables and tasks relevant to this deliverable

1.2 Key terms described

In this report, we use several rather complex terms frequently. Here we provide their description or definition:

- **Open data ecosystem:** “a cyclical, sustainable, demand-driven environment oriented around agents that are mutually interdependent in the creation and delivery of value from open data” (Van Loenen et al. (2018, p. 5).
- **Open data ecosystem drivers:** (1) user driven, (2) circular, (3) inclusive, and (4) skill-based:
 - **User driven:** User driven focus on the user needs and demands for the data, such as what data they need, in which format, how is the potential use and reuse.
 - **Inclusive:** an inclusive ODE allows any actor to participate in the ODE: “The inclusion of problem owners, i.e., citizens, public administrators, interest groups with a clear view of critical problems to solve, would instead call for an open and broader process based on participation and co-creation. The interaction with industry partners, civil society, and governments is essential to ensure that open data initiatives are inclusive. Inclusive ODEs address society's needs at large by ensuring individuals and disadvantaged groups (including elderly, women, disabled) have access to and benefit

¹ Please note that the skill-based driver was not part of the granted ODECO project. It was introduced later in the project (see Van Loenen et al., 2021)

from today's growing knowledge and information society. Making ODEs more inclusive becomes possible by (a) creating the necessary skills to use Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and (b) enabling access through specific easy to use applications, having public interest and the needs of the whole society in mind." (Van Loenen et al., 2021, p. 7).

- **Circular:** "An open data ecosystem is circular [...] when data is opened by data providers and then processed so that intermediaries, value-adding resellers, and enrichers can keep processed data in use for as long as possible." (Van Loenen et al., 2021, p. 6). A circular open data ecosystem envisions to fairly create and distribute open data values among the stakeholders as per their induced efforts, times, and other resources. In this deliverable, circularity focuses on non-government entities utilizing Open Government Data (OGD) and contributing enhanced OGD back to the ODE as open data, fostering a circular process of value creation and fair value distribution.
- **Skill-based:** skill-based ODEs focus on the capacity building of the open data actors. This will fill in the gap to use the open data effectively. This is not limited to data use but also building knowledge in the researchers, governments, and businesses to better design and implement policies in making the open data use in the best way possible.
- **Strategies and approaches:** Planned and deliberate actions or approaches to achieve a sustainable and value-creating ODE.

1.3 Structure of this deliverable

The deliverable is organized as follows: Section 2 develops and explains the methodology. Section 3 explains the existing research gaps in open data systems and how we propose to fill these gaps by designing ODEs. Section 4 repurposes the data collected from the research per driver. Section 5 presents the ODE framework, designed by the project, summarising key components of ODEs. Section 6 synthesizes the key strategies to arrive at sustainable ODE. Section 7 provides policy recommendations to drive ODEs. Section 8 summarizes the conclusions.

2 Methodology

This deliverable builds upon the previous ODECO deliverables. The methodology for this deliverable spans over to 4 steps (see Figure 2). The first step is the preliminary preparatory research, followed by the 2nd step, the data collection. The 3rd step is the analysis of the collected data, and the 4th step is the analysis of the strategic approaches with respect to their involvement in the ODE framework and drivers.

Figure 2: Methodology for developing strategies and approaches to ODEs

In the subsequent subsections, we will elaborate on each step. Our methodology is aligned with the inductive research methodology for the qualitative analysis of data. The inductive research approach serves the purpose of condensing the collected data into a more concise and summarized form, establishing a link between these brief summaries and the overall objectives of the study, and, lastly, developing a framework related to strategies that are supported by the data collected in the first step (Thomas, 2006).

2.1 Preliminary research

In the first step of the methodology, we performed a literature review, to identify gaps in the current open data systems. After identifying these gaps, we mapped them to the ODE drivers. We also extracted elements from the other ODECO deliverables to identify the key elements that required further development in terms of strategies, or that could contribute to the design of an ODE framework.

2.2 Data collection

We relied on different data sources to design an ODEs framework, its components, and related strategies. We collected data from the deliverables and research (see Figure 1). We further considered any important remarks, recommendations, conclusions, or key outcomes regarding ODE drivers raised in organised workshops. The Task Leader explained to the ESRs and supervisors how they should collect the relevant key elements from the deliverables and expand this search to their individual research work. The key elements collected using predefined metadata were shared via an excel sheet (see Table 1 for an example). In this way, we collected 83 key elements.

We analysed the data with respect to key-elements, ODE's drivers, ODE framework's connections, and synthesized the strategies into meaningful and fathomable visualizations.

Table 1: A sample strategy for inclusive open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Drivers (User driven, circular, inclusive, skill-based)	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
There should be continued focus on publication of open government datasets by public administration.	To realize the value of open data, it is important that high-quality open datasets are easily available. Accordingly, non-government parties should continue to release open datasets, based on legal mandates as well as on a voluntary basis. To ensure that public administrations prioritize release of open data, it may be important to evaluate different enforcement as well as incentive structures.	Inclusive	Enabling Environment (Regulations)	Continued implementation of legal mandates for non-open government data

We have also collected consortium feedback to improve the key elements, and to refine the ODE framework, components, and strategies through the workshops (see Table 2). The workshops conducted by keeping in view the co-creation technique where ESRs and supervisors worked together in collaborative way to design the ODE framework and extract strategies towards sustainable and value-creating ODEs (Sanders & Stappers, 2008).

Table 2: Workshops conducted for framework design and identification of strategies

Topics/purpose of workshops	Participants	Date
In an online interactive session, deliverable leader Introduced the very initial version of the deliverable and analysis framework to extract the key elements as explained in Table 1.	ODECO Consortium — ESRs and Supervisors	13 November 2024
Intermediate workshop to review the collected information regarding the ODE framework design and the identification strategies.	ODECO Consortium — ESRs and Supervisors	3 December 2024
In an online interactive session, the leader of the deliverable shared the collected strategy and initial version of the ODE framework. The participants reflected on the missing components or adding new components in the ODE framework. Moreover, the interaction among the ODE framework components was discussed in detail.	ODECO Consortium — ESRs and Supervisors	17 December 2024
In an online interactive session, the leader of the deliverable presented the initial draft version of the deliverable and shared the analysis performed on the collected data and results achieved. The deliverable leader asked the participants to explain the individual components (simple description, state-of-the-art, and beyond state-of-the-art) of the ODE framework. Furthermore, participants were asked to explain the ODE strategies in a better way, such as giving a title to the strategy and explaining in 2-3 small paragraphs each strategy that was discussed with the participants.	ODECO Consortium — ESRs and Supervisors	17 January 2025

2.3 Analysis

We used quantitative and qualitative methods to analyse the collected data to obtain the required results. We performed quantitative analysis (pivot table) of the responses received from the respondents regarding the key elements of an ODE framework, its strategies, and ODE drivers. For

qualitative analysis, we manually grouped based on the thematic analysis of the acquired information (e.g., from other deliverables and individual research work of the involved ESRs and supervisors). We transformed the collected data to retain only the unique entries of the strategies to reach a level of understanding. At this step, we aimed to design ODE frameworks, its components, and interactions. Furthermore, we presented the ODE drivers in the ODE framework and the corresponding strategies. The detailed flow chart for designing and strategizing the ODE framework have been illustrated in Figure 3. Figure 3 illustrates the process flow, which begins with two parallel tasks: identifying key elements from previous deliverables and identifying research gaps through a literature review on open data systems. The key elements are then linked to ODE drivers and used in designing the ODE framework. Similarly, the identified research gaps are also mapped to ODE drivers and incorporated into the framework design. Finally, the proposed strategies are mapped to the developed ODE framework, ensuring a structured approach to addressing the identified gaps.

2.4 Synthesis of strategies and approaches

In the last step, we synthesized the collected strategies into meaningful actions by giving them titles and identifying their relations to the ODE framework, its components, and drivers. We also grouped them based on their similarities and entitled them to similar approaches. We developed a clickable version pertaining to the ODE framework to make it easy to navigate through the ODE components and strategies. Furthermore, strategies are listed in clickable versions to design sustainable and value-creating ODE.

Figure 3: Methodology for the designing the open data ecosystem framework

3 Preliminary Research – Identification of Challenges

3.1 Current open data systems and challenges in the literature

Many studies have explored the concepts of open data and ODEs. The motivation behind each study differs with respect to the ODE elements. A collective paper by Van Loenen et al. (2021) identified that current open data systems are supplier-driven, exclusive, linear, and effort-based. Transforming the current open data systems from supplier-driven to user driven, exclusive to inclusive, linear to circular, and effort-based to skill-based, can open the way towards value-creating and sustainable ODEs.

A study by Wiener et al. (2016) explored how ODEs can help in thriving society, more specifically, the neuroscience field. They mention that the open data landscape depends upon the technological, cultural, practical, nature of open data and the availability of resources, and the open data marketplace while sharing open data. In the neuroscience field, open data sharing with other researchers is important, but it was hindered with the issues related to data sharing, discoverability, and incentives to motivate the data providers. Cultivating the ODE for neuroscience can begin by incentivizing the researchers to share their experimental data. Without incentivizing the researchers, the ODE will not thrive irrespective of the effort being made to build it. Secondly, data should be discoverable by other researchers in the field. If data is not discoverable, not only incentivizing the data efforts to be fruitful. Third, ODEs need to be sustainable, well-governed with a well-managed data-life cycle and supportive towards integrated and coordinated developments. All the above-mentioned points regarding data sharing, discoverability and development of a marketplace pose challenges to the ODE realization (Wiener et al., 2016) and inspired ODE's research to design sustainable ODEs.

Open data brings opportunities in the form of the development of new products and services. A major challenge is the collaboration among the actors involved in the open data provision, consumption, and service and application developments. These integrated and coordinated efforts brought open data to the creation of ODEs and the development of business models specific to open data. Kitsios et al. (2017) presented a new perspective to involve the stakeholders in the Thessaloniki ODEs for the creation of entrepreneurship opportunities. They have also focused on dedicated efforts to create a value chain in the ODE to influence actors among themselves. Furthermore, they have explained that bad-quality data provision and permanency makes it inconvenient for the actors to use the data (Kitsios et al., 2017).

Another foundational paper (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014) explained the elements of an ODE and infrastructure to bring innovation through open data. Their four key elements of an ODEs are: 1) Making open data available through the internet 2) Functionalities such as data search, findability, data view and evaluation along with licenses details, 3) Providing data cleaning, data analysis, data enriching, combining and linking and visualizing data operations 4) Facilitating the interpretation and discussion regarding data and completing feedback loops to the data provider and other stakeholders. Furthermore, to better integrate and present the four elements as a whole, three further elements required to be implemented: 5) user manuals showing the possible use of data 6) quality management system, and 7) metadata management system (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). The paper also found challenges related to ODEs such as policy, licenses, technological, financing, organizational, cultural, and legal frameworks influenced by ICT infrastructures. ODEs can possibly be established by user adaptability, feedback loops, dynamic interactions between suppliers and users, and several other interrelated aspects. According to the paper, research on ODEs is more fragmented, and focus is mostly on the open data users and producers instead of focusing on all-inclusive functioning of ODEs.

The value creation in the ODE is a wicked problem due to complex interactions among the involved stakeholders, lack of specific formulation and criteria deciding on what constitutes value and uncertain outcomes. Open data efforts often focus on open data publication instead of the use of open data, which creates the value (Zuiderwijk et al., 2016). Zuiderwijk et al., (2016) have explained that commercial value creation in ODEs requires certain policy guidelines from the governments regarding 1) capacity building related to contextual factors influencing the data use and commercial value creation, 2) focusing on the availability of resources such as open data, open IT, internal IT, knowledge, and governance, 3) cooperation development between businesses and citizens, and 4) reducing the negative effects of values created by companies in ODEs.

Open data has the potential to enhance public institutions, such as universities, by improving efficiency, effectiveness, and the quality of research and education systems through a shared open database for critical investigation and interpretation. In a study by van Schalkwyk et al. (2016), the authors proposed an ecosystem approach to governance, aiming to create order out of a complex and cyclic set of processes. They achieved this by applying the lenses of a conceptual framework to represent the South African public university governance ODE (van Schalkwyk et al., 2016). They are also uncertain about the supply and demand balance in the ODEs. The collection, transformation, and provision of data in appropriate contexts and formats require the availability of critical resources to maximize the likelihood of Open Data (OD) use and impact². They also stated that, in the case of the ODE in public institutions (universities), external funding is required to support intermediaries working within the ecosystem, providing open data, and performing actions sustainably.

A study by Styrin et al., (2017) compared open government data ecosystem efforts in the USA, Russia, and Mexico through three lenses: Government Policy Framework and Institutional Structures, Government Data Management, and Stakeholder Engagement with Open Data. They observed policy variations in ODEs at the international level and noted that open government data ecosystems face challenges in institutionalizing OGD programs in these countries. Runeson et al., (2021) have mentioned that ODE requires involvement from both public and commercial organizations as actors. They have mentioned challenges being faced by the ODE such as technical, legal, and organizational. For instance, legal and privacy challenges when organizations share data among themselves, selecting business models and strategies to decide upon the data opening and closing for competitive advantages, and utilizing technical solutions to share the data efficiently and securely. They have synthesized the ODE based on data value, governance, data intrinsics, and evaluation from the empirical data. They have evaluated ODE aspects (Open Data Types, value of data, value of collaboration, acquisition, relationships, competition, quality, maturity, and legal) using three cases (Runeson et al., 2021).

Transparency in ODEs is an essential element to be considered to develop the smart cities concept as mentioned in the study by (Lnenicka et al., 2022), they have explored the transparency by design in the ODEs and evaluated the maturity of ODE in 22 smart cities by evaluating the 34 portals through the 36 features. Through a developed framework to determine the transparency in ODE, they have ranked the portals into four categories such as developed, defined, managed, and integrated. An ODE in smart cities has been conceptualized. ODE ecosystems should provide data innovation capabilities while fostering data literacy, cross-boundary collaboration, participation, and data access. Furthermore, open and innovation ecosystems align with the needs and motivations of smart city stakeholders, supporting data-driven economic development where data contributes to policy improvements and informed decision-making (Gupta et al., 2020).

² <https://scholarsarchive.library.albany.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1073&context=ctg>

To summarise the analysis, the limitations of current open data systems—such as being supplier-driven, exclusive, linear, and effort-based—hinder their sustainability and value creation (Van Loenen, Zuiderwijk, Vancauwenberghe, et al., 2021). Challenges related to data discoverability, stakeholder collaboration, governance, and quality further impede the effectiveness of open data initiatives (Kitsios et al., 2017; Wiener et al., 2016). Additionally, issues such as policy fragmentation, lack of feedback loops, and insufficient incentives for data sharing make it difficult to establish a well-functioning open data landscape (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014, 2016). The absence of a structured, transparent, and collaborative framework within open data systems results in inefficient data use, limiting its potential for economic growth, policy improvements, and innovation (Gupta et al., 2020; Lnenicka et al., 2022). Therefore, transitioning towards a sustainable ODE is not just beneficial but essential. By integrating governance structures, stakeholder engagement, data value mechanisms, and sustainability measures, ODEs can address the shortcomings of traditional open data systems, ensuring that open data is not only published but effectively utilized to generate economic, social, and policy-driven impact. The full list of challenges of current open data systems is presented in Figure 4. The challenges were extracted from the literature (Van Loenen et al., 2021; Gupta et al., 2020; Lnenicka et al., 2022; Kitsios et al., 2017; Wiener et al., 2016; Runeson et al., 2021; Styrin et al., 2017; van Schalkwyk et al., 2016; Zuiderwijk et al., 2016; Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). Furthermore, these limitations are technical, organizational, and governance- and policy-related. In the end, we proposed that an ODEs framework, along with actionable strategies and approaches, can effectively address these challenges and lead to a sustainable and value-creating ODE.

Figure 4: Identified challenges in open data systems and dealing with them through designing and strategizing ODE framework

3.2 Mapping the identified challenges in open data systems to the Open Data Ecosystems' drivers

The identified challenges have been categorized based on ODE drivers, aiming to find solutions through these drivers. For example, how open data drivers address these challenges and by what means. Specifically, the user driven approach in an ODE enhances adaptability, scalability, and innovation by ensuring data is discoverable, high-quality, and efficiently shared with stakeholders as per their needs. Some challenges are cross-cutting and require continuous efforts to be resolved, such as infrastructure, resources, governance, and skills; this we call horizontal challenges. The vertical challenges are those that we can easily map to the ODE drivers somehow by understanding their scope and relevance. For instance, challenges with adaptability, scalability,

data discoverability, quality, and innovation-oriented data are mapped to the user driven driver of the ODE. Similarly, the remaining current open data systems challenges as mentioned in Figure 4 are mapped to the user driven, inclusive, and circular drivers of the ODE. The mapping institutions come from the explanations of each challenge as described throughout this section.

Table 3: Identified challenges in open data systems and mapping them to the open data ecosystem's drivers

Vertical challenges		
User driven	Inclusive	Circular
Adaptable	Transparent	Sustainable
Scalable	Collaborative	Value driven
Discoverable data	Clear Boundaries	Clear roles of involved stakeholders
Efficient Data sharing	Involving organizations	Interoperable
Quality	Not limited to governments	Economic value-creation
Innovation oriented		Clear Boundaries
Horizontal challenges		
Infrastructure		
Resources		
Governance		
Skill based		

4 Data Collection

We analysed ODECO reports and the research results of the ODECO ESRs to identify the components and their connections within the ecosystem framework, and propose strategies. Descriptions of proposed strategies were requested from the ESRs and supervisors for each element (we considered any important remarks, recommendations, conclusions, or key outcomes regarding ODE drivers and subsequent benefits related to these drivers as key elements) for the purpose of their inclusion and implementation in the ODE framework. In this way, our aim was to identify and understand the components of the ODE framework and their relevance to the ODE drivers and how they may further contribute to strategies for achieving a sustainable ODE.

The data collected included identified strategies stemming from conducted individual ODECO research and collective deliverables, which directly or indirectly improve the ODEs. The summary of the strategies for corresponding ODE drivers are explained below (for detailed information we refer to annex 1 Table 4, Table 5, Table 6, and Table 7).

4.1 User driven strategies

The strategies outlined for enhancing ODEs emphasize the importance of collaboration, shared culture, accessibility, and sustainability. Public administrations and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) could form partnerships to co-develop open data initiatives, sharing knowledge and resources to respond to the evolving needs of stakeholders. Cultivating an organizational culture that values open data and ensuring data quality through profiling, feedback mechanisms, and user driven interfaces can improve accessibility and usability. Furthermore, integrating open data across domains and adhering to technical standards, FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and interoperable) principles (GO FAIR, 2016), and CARE principles (Research Data Alliance International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group., 2019) promote interoperability and facilitate seamless data sharing. Building open data communities and providing training opportunities for users will help develop capacity and foster greater engagement. Supporting open licenses, ethical considerations in data sharing (e.g., privacy and confidentiality), and transparency in legal frameworks is essential to ensuring responsible and sustainable data reuse. Lastly, ensuring the economic sustainability of ODEs through diverse funding (public, private and hybrid) models is expected to support their long-term success. Collectively, these strategies aim to create ODEs that are user driven, interoperable, and responsive to the needs of various users, ultimately contributing to their broader impact and sustainability.

4.2 Inclusive strategies

The strategies for enhancing ODEs from the inclusive perspective emphasize the importance of non-government data publication, shared infrastructures, and multi-format data access. There is a focus on addressing barriers to local community access, supporting non-governmental contributions, and aligning the interests of diverse stakeholders to foster collaboration. Recommendations include community centric design, lowering data access barriers, and creating governance mechanisms for bottom-up initiatives. Furthermore, interdisciplinary collaboration, the design of inclusive open data events, and the institutionalization of these events are crucial. Legal frameworks should account for power dynamics and promote equity, integrating CARE principles alongside FAIR. Additionally, the availability of platforms for non-government open data is encouraged, with the suggestion of establishing a consortium for collective open data sharing and governance.

In this deliverable, inclusiveness mainly focuses on *open data* contributions from the non-government data. However, this view appears too limited. Inclusivity should not be restricted to providing open data to the ODE; rather, it should encompass any valuable contribution from non-government actors to the ODE—this may include new datasets, tools, insights, services, or

collaborative practices that enhance the ecosystem as a whole. Recognizing these broader contributions reflects a more comprehensive and realistic understanding of what sustains an ODE over time. This marks an important shift from our initial perception of inclusivity and a more mature interpretation of sustainable ODEs.

In addition, the inclusivity concept should be reconsidered to include also dataset inclusivity, as true inclusiveness in open data goes beyond who contributes data—it must also ensure that the data itself reflects diverse contexts, needs, and populations, particularly those often underrepresented or marginalized in data collection and sharing processes. Therefore, dataset inclusivity should also be considered in this context.

4.3 Circular strategies

The strategies outline efforts to enhance the circularity of ODEs by promoting equitable value distribution. Strategies include fostering collaboration among governments, NGOs, and businesses, adopting open standards, and validating metadata. Another strategy to drive participation in the ODE is to incentivize participation both financially and non-financially. Additionally, leveraging intermediaries through advisory services is crucial for facilitating data sharing and integration, while promoting the use of open-source software further supports these efforts.

In this deliverable (and the overall project), circularity has primarily focused on non-government (NG) actors utilizing Open Government Data (OGD) and contributing enhanced versions back to the ODE, thereby creating a loop of value creation and fair distribution. However, also this view appears too limited. Circularity should not be restricted to the return of improved OGD alone; rather, it should encompass any valuable contribution from open (government) data users back to the open data ecosystem (including the open data provider). This may include improved open (government) datasets, but also tools, new insights, services, or collaborative practices that enhance the ecosystem as a whole. Recognizing these broader contributions reflects a more comprehensive and realistic understanding of what sustains an ODE over time. This marks an important shift from our initial perception of circularity and a more mature interpretation of sustainable ODEs.

4.4 Skill based strategies

The strategies related to the skill-based drivers of the ODE emphasize capacity building, data quality enhancement, and the empowerment of intermediaries through accessible tools. These strategies include initiatives such as providing data augmentation tools to improve data reliability and trust, as well as developing low-code platforms to support educators and data intermediaries in fostering broader participation and usability across diverse data environments. Strengthening skills and capabilities within the ecosystem is essential for ensuring sustainable and effective open data utilization.

5 Analysis - Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem Framework

The capabilities of open data ecosystems come with challenges in realizing their full potential. By analysing these challenges and leveraging research conducted individually and in deliverables within this project and beyond, we designed an open data ecosystem (ODE) framework.

5.1 Designing the Open Data Ecosystem (ODE) framework

The first attempt to design the ODE framework was made in Ali et al. (2025). For this deliverable, we adapted the ODE framework of Ali et al., (2025) with the help of interactive workshops and co-creation techniques by asking workshop participants to reflect on the proposed ODE framework and its components.

In the first workshop, the initial version of the framework was explained to the participants, asking their opinions on the placement of components and their connections with other components. Some components were renamed, deleted, or enriched through the discussion. In the subsequent two workshops, we further improved the framework and added policies, challenges, and recommendations. Another example of the changes is that, initially, governance was not included as a component in the original framework. However, after the workshops governance was incorporated.

Figure 5 presents a preliminary set of ODE framework components along with the beyond-state-of-the-art work required for each component. Each of them is explained in more detail below.

Figure 5: components of a sustainable Open Data Ecosystem framework

5.2 Explaining sustainable open data ecosystem framework's components

5.2.1 Open Data Ecosystem

Description: The ODE is considered pivotal for sustainable value creation through open data utilization. In this study, it is used as an umbrella term, as shown in Figure 5, and with the inner red circle encompassing all major components that play a direct or indirect role in the ODE's sustainable value creation. The ODE is comprised of a dynamic environment covering aspects related to open data stakeholders, driving forces, value creation, governance, and open data infrastructure. The motive behind the design of the ODE is to identify all components and their dynamic connections. Furthermore, the identification of malfunctions in the current ecosystem will allow for the proposition of the appropriate strategic approaches in order to establish a well-functioning ODE. In ODEs, stakeholder groups work collaboratively to stimulate the potential of

open data. Despite the potential of ODEs, they face several challenges regarding the standardization of tools, techniques, and methods for implementing open data initiatives, as well as generating value through the use and reuse of open data based on needs and requirements. Addressing these challenges can enhance value creation and support the sustainability of the ODE.

State of the art: Several studies have explored the concept of ODEs (Styrin et al., 2017; Van Loenen, Zuiderwijk, Vancauwenberghe, et al., 2021; Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). ODE concepts are at very beginning stage of development, facing challenges with proper actor inclusion and roles, value-creation, value-distribution, user-needs elicitation, quality of data, utilization of artificial intelligence, adding value to the open data, and making all these steps transparent within ODEs and beyond. Open data systems face challenges to achieve value-creation and sustainability due to supply and demand mismatch, exclusion of certain user groups and domains, linear value-creation, and lack of skills have been explored at domain and country level such as finance, legal, education, geographic, and agricultural (Van Loenen, Zuiderwijk, Vancauwenberghe, et al., 2021). Open data impacts and its realization depends on stimulation of technical, social, and political resources, beyond the data supply but also making a contribution chain of activities around the datasets (Davies, 2011). The ODE complexity and challenge space observed from its multifaceted and multiprofessional nature and even gets multiplied when heterogeneity from the data, domains, and actors and each of them having their own specific challenges at different spatial and temporal levels gets into this.

Beyond the state of the art: We have examined the diversified nature of ODE concepts and associated challenges with them, which suggests a clear need for the ODE framework creation — containing all the major components. The role of ODE framework's components in stimulating the ODE drivers. Furthermore, proposing and formalizing strategies for each ODE framework's components, so that actual ODE can be sustained and value-creating for all involved actors. Additionally, emerging AI technologies, such as the open-source AI models, can both benefit from and contribute to ODEs. The formalization of ODE frameworks and corresponding strategies would be one step towards achieving sustainability and value-creating ODEs.

5.2.2 Open data infrastructure

Description: The technological components of ODEs, including tools, standards, services, and software applications, support data storage, sharing, and operations such as data integration and interoperability across diverse data domains, form the infrastructure of ODEs. Open data infrastructure reinforces the entire ODE by enabling smooth data sharing and supporting collaborative activities. Open data infrastructure faces challenges with the advancement of technologies, such as existing usage of obsolete technologies and unstandardized practices.

State of the art: Several studies emphasize the importance of scalable and interoperable infrastructures to ensure the sustainability of ODEs. Kirstein et al., (2020) describe the idea of large-scale open data management platforms based on semantic web technologies. Conde et al., (2024) further explore metadata-driven integration of open data portals into data spaces, advocating for automated metadata generation and validation through standardized models. Grossman et al., (2016) propose the data commons model, which co-locates data, storage, and computational resources with common analysis tools, emphasizing persistent digital identifiers, metadata services, APIs, and data portability for interoperability. Collectively, these studies underscore the need for modern, scalable, and standardized open data infrastructures that leverage semantic technologies, metadata-driven integration, and interoperable frameworks to enhance the effectiveness and long-term viability of ODEs.

Beyond the state of the art: The future of ODEs could embrace adaptive and self-optimizing data infrastructures that evolve in response to real-time conditions and user interactions, what we could define as living open data infrastructures. Unlike traditional open data repositories, which rely on periodic updates and manual interventions, living open data infrastructures would incorporate machine learning, automation, and feedback loops to enhance data quality, relevance, and interoperability dynamically. By integrating AI-driven mechanisms, open datasets could learn from usage patterns, detect inconsistencies, and refine their structure and content based on community contributions and contextual changes. This approach would foster greater responsiveness, accuracy, and efficiency, ensuring that open data remains continuously updated and aligned with user needs. Moreover, self-optimizing datasets could enhance cross-domain interoperability by adapting to evolving data standards and seamlessly integrating new information sources. However, realizing this vision requires addressing key challenges, such as transparency in algorithmic decision-making, and safeguards against biases in automated learning processes. Additionally, governance frameworks would need to balance openness with reliability, ensuring that self-optimizing datasets remain verifiable and accountable to the broader open data community. By embracing living open data infrastructures, future ODEs could move beyond static data repositories, enabling a more dynamic, intelligent, and sustainable approach to data sharing and collaboration.

5.2.3 Enabling environment

Description: Enabling the environment is meant to cover aspects of sustainable ODE such as open data market (e.g., business models for sustainability), culture, regulations, and other capacity building, and community participation activities that support or hinder the success of open data initiatives. Community participation is important as ODEs assume the utilization of data outside the systems that generated them to create value. The proper arrangements of the enabling requirements reduce barriers to open data sharing and use, promote FAIR principles, drive innovation, and foster transparency across diverse cultural contexts. In the enabling environment there is relevant to consider the ethical considerations such as bias, privacy concerns, and misuse of open data (Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2014b).

State of the art: It is important to understand that any enablement requirement is part of a bigger system of values in which the definition of transparency and participation is negotiated. Knowledge production is political and shaped by power dynamics that enable or limit participation in open data initiatives (Bates, 2013; Johnson, 2014; Kitchin, 2024). More specifically, some actors lack the skills to make sense of open data (Perovich et al., 2020). This is particularly true for marginalized communities who cannot actively participate in open data initiatives or who might not be represented by data due to data gaps (Milan, 2020; Ruijter et al., 2024). Further, AI and data infrastructures complicate and dilute the process of tracing data origins, making value assessment challenging (Publications Office of the European Union., 2024). Power imbalances shape data access and usage, leading to selective openness, where dominant actors (e.g., corporations) benefit more than smaller entities or individuals (Broomfield, 2023; Gurstein, 2011).

Beyond the state of the art: Starting from the consideration that ODEs also bring conflicts among values, different governance strategies can be envisaged in terms of the study and practice of ODEs: Study the extent to which open data regulations mandate or promote data sharing that is not meant to be repurposed in the data economy. For instance, the implementing regulation on High-Value Datasets (2023/138) prioritizes economic value, thus enabling greater economic/market value rather than other values, such as participation (Broomfield, 2023). Understand the role of commercial actors in open data by adding obligations for open data sharing in the public interest, as seen in Barcelona's 'data sovereignty clauses,' which require private service providers to share data in an open, machine-readable format within procurement contracts (Monge et al., 2022). Rely on private law mechanisms to promote equitable data use, as

in the case of stronger share-alike obligations that prevent the risk of open data exploitation (Data Science Law Lab, 2024).

5.2.4 Governance

Description: Major element of ODE, deals with setting the roles, defining rules of open data initiatives and open data itself, and mechanisms for open data handling (managing open data responsibly, justifiably, and durably) throughout open data life cycle and beyond. This sets the rules such as resolving conflicts and power imbalances among stakeholders (data providers, intermediaries, and users), preserving accountability, adopting/developing standards. Good governance leads the ODE to essential components such as trust, data quality, and FAIR use of open data. Open data governance is opaque, with accountability dispersed across private-public partnerships (J. Taylor, 2017; L. Taylor et al., 2022). This lack of transparency makes it difficult to track data movement, integrity, and security, leading to risks such as unintended data repurposing (e.g., U.S. open science data used for facial recognition in China) (L. Taylor et al., 2022).

State of the art: Governance in ODEs is essential for maintaining sustainable data sharing and reuse among stakeholders, including governments, businesses, and individuals (Pollock, 2011; Van Loenen, Zuidervijk, Vancauwenberghe et al., 2021). Traditional governance models have largely followed hierarchical and market-based mechanisms (Chantillon et al., 2017; Santoro et al., 2024), but research highlights the benefits of participatory, commons-based approaches (Gurnstein, 2011; Ostrom, 1990), aiming for greater inclusivity and efficiency. ODE governance must balance regulation, stakeholder involvement, and sustainable data sharing. Hierarchical models rely on strict regulations, ensuring compliance but limiting adaptability (Weerakkody, Janssen, et al., 2017). Market-based governance uses financial incentives to encourage participation but may exclude resource-limited actors (Moore, 1993, 2006). Network-based governance fosters collaboration and trust (Provan & Kenis, 2008), but can suffer from coordination issues (Johnson, 2014). A growing body of research supports commons-based governance, following Ostrom's (1990) self-governing principles. This approach promotes boundary-making, shared decision-making, and legal frameworks for sustainability (Davies & Perini, 2016). Commons-based governance facilitates collective management of data resources, improving accessibility and fostering innovation (Cavanillas et al., 2016).

Non-governmental data holders face barriers in ODEs, including legal, financial, and technical challenges (Reggi & Dawes, 2022a). Many private entities hesitate to share data due to intellectual property concerns and competitive risks (European Commission, 2020). To address these issues, governance strategies must provide regulatory clarity and incentives. Policy interventions such as mandatory data-sharing for publicly funded research or tax benefits for businesses that contribute data can bridge gaps (Weerakkody, Kapoor, et al., 2017). Collaborative platforms enable businesses, NGOs, and researchers to negotiate agreements, fostering trust and mutual benefits (Chantillon et al., 2017). Empirical studies indicate that public-private partnerships improve data-sharing practices (Hossain et al., 2016).

User engagement is crucial for ODE sustainability, requiring contributions beyond data consumption (Yuan, 2019). Barriers such as limited technical literacy, lack of awareness, and unclear feedback mechanisms hinder participation (Huijboom & Van den Broek, 2011). Motivation theories offer insight into engagement. Self-Determination Theory underscores autonomy, competence, and social connection as key drivers (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Users contribute more when their efforts have meaningful impact and when platforms are user-friendly and rewarding (Wenger, 1998). Fostering communities of practice strengthens engagement by encouraging knowledge-sharing and innovation (Bachtar et al., 2020). Effective governance should include gamification, recognition systems, and streamlined contribution mechanisms (Davies & Perini, 2016). Open data portals allowing user annotations and dataset updates improve participation (Safarov et al., 2017b). Partnerships with educational institutions and advocacy groups further enhance long-term user engagement (Hossain et al., 2016).

Beyond the state of the art: Governance frameworks must evolve to address emerging challenges like data sovereignty, AI in decision-making, and the digital divide (Kitchin & Lauriault, 2014). Hybrid models combining hierarchical, market-based, and commons-based approaches can provide regulatory compliance while fostering innovation and collaboration (Micheli et al., 2020; Van Dijck et al., 2018). AI-driven compliance mechanisms can streamline governance by monitoring data-sharing agreements, while blockchain-based smart contracts can enhance transparency (Davies & Perini, 2016; Gurnstein, 2011). However, these technologies must be implemented carefully to prevent exacerbating power asymmetries (Ruijter et al., 2024) and environmental footprint. Ensuring inclusivity in ODE governance remains vital. Marginalized groups often face obstacles in data access and contribution, reinforcing inequalities (Meijer & Potjer, 2018). Policies promoting digital literacy and community-led governance can help address these disparities (Ruijter et al., 2024). Governance strategies must prioritize equity, ensuring open data benefits are widely distributed and decision-making remains inclusive.

5.2.5 Resources

Description: Resources of ODEs cover dimensions like datasets, metadata models, tools, and funding to manage the data, and analytical models which can support data accessibility and usability across wider domains. These resources are important to attain innovation and benefit from open data. Better resource management, allocation, and utilization are required to ensure transparency and accountability of the ODE for fair value creation and distribution.

State of the art: According to the Open Data Barometer³, open data initiatives that have support from the government and sustainable availability and access to required resources have a high chance of achieving their defined goals and impact. Open data initiatives development and implementation needs continuous availability of resources (e.g., finance) (Donker & van Loenen, 2017). Data curation and sharing solutions are considered important and they provide solution for “a common metadata tracking framework, providing tools and resources to create and manage large, heterogeneous data sets in a coherent manner, and allowing users of (parts of) data sets to ‘connect the metadata dots” (Sansone et al., 2012). The data resources and tools are considered a characteristic of an ODE (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). The data resources cover several aspects, including licensing, linked data, data packaging, patching, pull requests, and data merging options. The data resources should also include ICT preparedness, ICT usage, architecture, and resource allocation (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014).

A study by Zuiderwijk et al. (2016) mentions that open data policies should be oriented and pay attention to the availability and quality of five types of resources: open data, open information technology, internal IT, required knowledge, and governance. Resources on the open data producer's side are needed, but some resources are also needed on the data user's side, such as open datasets, the skills required to analyse the data, stakeholder collaboration and network effects, and competitive advantage based on open data. Open data resources required to create a competitive advantage have also been discussed in the study by Zuiderwijk et al. (2016). Even companies can acquire the required resources from their allies to generate commercial value in ODEs. Resources from different companies may lead to value creation and give companies an opportunity to rely on specific resources that are important to them. The need for resources also varies from company to company. Resource needs are also expandable for all stakeholders to some extent.

Beyond the state of the art: The availability of resources is mostly focused on the producer's side, and less attention is given to the open data users and intermediaries' side. There is also a need for funding models to cover public-private partnerships and open innovations. It's also crucial that sustainable funding is provided for other parts of the ODE, including data

³ <http://opendatabarometer.org/>

infrastructure, governance, and community engagement. We have seen studies that discuss data packaging and patching, but cross-platform interoperability remains an issue. Work is required toward the development of a standardized resource framework covering different kinds of resources (technical, social, financial, and even human). Considering social capital as a quantifiable resource in ODEs is also important.

5.2.6 Stakeholder groups

Stakeholder groups can be categorized into three groups: producers, intermediaries, and users. The producer's stakeholder group is responsible for data generation and provision through the ODE. The intermediaries' stakeholder groups are responsible for a diverse type of tasks such as intermediating, training, or developing applications. Finally, user stakeholder groups are using open data as per their need and developing applications or making decisions based on open data.

Roles may overlap across different actor groups. For instance, citizens can serve as data providers (such as through platforms like OpenStreetMap), while also being data users and beneficiaries of open data initiatives. Similarly, application developers frequently take on multiple roles as intermediaries, users, and enablers who contribute to both the technical and functional layers of the ecosystem. Academia is another cross-cutting actor, actively involved in data provision, stewardship, advocacy, and research, thereby influencing both policy and practice. Furthermore, data users are not per se passive recipients—they often provide feedback that shapes data quality and relevance and simultaneously benefit from the insights and services enabled by open data. This fluidity of roles underscores the dynamic and interconnected nature of the open data landscape. In some cases, it has also been seen that roles and actors could be the same, for instance, intermediaries can also be enablers/ data steward.

Producers

Description: This group of stakeholders are responsible for generating and providing open data. They are also known as data providers (Heijlen & Cromptvoets, 2021) or data publishers (Charalabidis et al., n.d.; Hrustek et al., 2023). Their role is to make sure that the data being produced is relevant, useful, accurate, and accessible to the other stakeholders. They require to maintain data quality and adherence to data maintenance aspects all along the way of data life cycle.

State of the art: They are responsible for the open data supply in the ODE, and this open data supply is considered their best effort contributed to the ecosystem. They are responsible for dataset creation or generation (Buteau et al., 2018; Oliveira et al., 2017) and/or publishing (Corbett et al., 2020) open data to fulfil end-user demands in the ODE. They may share open data with intermediaries to enrich the data and prepare it (Alexopoulos et al., 2014). Data provision is not always based on demand and needs. Data should be considered for publication if it can be used for service development for citizens, provide value to companies, or contribute to economic improvement (Köster & Suárez, 2016). Often, open data producers are required to develop a framework (legal or regulatory) pertaining to data opening, data sharing, and data use (Dawes et al., 2016; Fang et al., 2024). Governments are the most common providers of open data, but a few studies also mention businesses or private enterprises as open data producers (see, for example, Ali et al., 2024).

Beyond the state of the art: In the ODE, the inclusive nature of an ODE emphasizes data provision from non-governmental sources (Van Loenen, Zuiderwijk, Vancauwenberghe, et al., 2021). Data integration techniques should be adopted so that new datasets can be generated from existing ones. The provision of high-quality and demand-oriented datasets can contribute to value creation and sustainability in ODEs. Non-governmental organizations should also be included as

part of the producers' stakeholder group, rather than relying solely on governments to provide all required datasets.

Intermediaries

Description: Open data intermediaries provide specialized resources to enhance the supply, flow, and reuse of open data and the connection between various open data stakeholders. Various actors can take up the role of open data intermediaries, including government organizations, businesses, non-profit organizations, media organizations, and research organizations.

State of the art: Open data intermediaries are often characterized as being the “bridge” between open data providers and end-users by (pre-)processing open data to facilitate its reuse. Nevertheless, in practice, open data intermediaries often offer more diverse kinds of products and services that improve the process of open data provision and re-use, sometimes without directly handling the data themselves. For example, some open data intermediaries offer software that facilitates open data providers to disseminate open data. Some others offer consulting services to open data providers and users. Media organizations have a more niche function; in addition to the traditional ways of providing open data, they act as communicators of open data to the public. As their main goal is to maximize their audience by providing accurate information, they translate open data insights into stories and visualizations that can be understood by the majority of their audience

Beyond the state of the art: Greater awareness and inspiration on the potential value-added services that can be offered based on/around open data should be promoted across various sectors/domains to encourage the emergence of more open data intermediaries that help address real-world challenges. Some potential collaborations between open data actors may happen with the help of open data intermediaries that bring different actors together or initiate possible connections or engagement. To some extent, federated architecture could address the current shortcomings where open data across different domains and/or jurisdictions are segmented due to multiple open data providers. The federated architecture means that users can easily integrate open data from multiple domains and/or jurisdictions based on interoperable data standards, but the maintenance of the data still falls under the responsibility of the original provider. This would be valuable to address complex global and local challenges requiring a multidisciplinary and multiscale data-based approach. Open data intermediaries can play a role in initiating or maintaining the federated architecture initiative. Certain open data actors may face financial constraints to purchase or subscribe proprietary software to supply, process, or reuse open data. Hence, the availability of open-source software may alleviate such constraints. Open data intermediaries could play a role in developing open-source software. Nevertheless, all these potential contributions of open data intermediaries require sustainable business models, especially if they were to be undertaken by government or non-profit organizations, which are, at the moment, often rely on sponsorship to carry out open data-related activities/initiatives.

Users

Description: The users stakeholder group consist of, but are not limited to, researchers, individuals, citizens, policymakers, businesses, and citizens. They utilize open data as the underlying benefit to making informed decisions and bringing innovations.

State of the art: A long list of open data users (governments, business, entrepreneurs, applications, developers, citizens, universities, researchers, civic hackers, civil society, and consumers) in ODEs (see Ali et al., 2025). They may also be referred to as data consumers (Köster & Suárez, 2016; Lee, 2014; Oliveira & Lóscio, 2018; van Schalkwyk et al., 2016), or data demanders (Charalabidis et al., n.d.). In OGD ecosystems, open data users actively participate in data downloading, browsing, and analysing to within an aim to develop services and applications which

could be commercial or for public good (Dawes et al., 2016; Fang et al., 2024). Data users can also be competitors within a particular domain of open data (Runeson et al., 2021). Data consumers can also be innovators in the ODE by innovating new applications and services by utilizing open data (Heijlen & Cromptoets, 2021). The data consumers also play a vital role in interpreting data and providing feedback on the datasets (Corbett et al., 2020).

5.2.7 Feedback/evaluation/redefinition

Description: Collecting feedback and evaluating the open data processes in ODEs are necessary to redefine the processes, requiring modifications to cope with the challenges related to ODEs. The feedback mechanisms are helpful in identifying the gaps, refining strategies/policies, and adapting to the varying external/internal needs. Additionally, feedback mechanisms are crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of the open data portals in promoting the quality of data and user participation. To complete the feedback loop, evaluation frameworks are critical for quantifying the results and impacts and aligning efforts with the objectives of an initiative. For long-term success and sustainability, robust and iterative feedback mechanisms, evaluation and redefinition of processes are vigorous.

State of the art: Herrera et al. (2023) argue that achieving user-centered evaluation hinges on the strategic adoption of the mental model concept (Herrera-Murillo et al., 2023). Mental models enable individuals to construct descriptions of a system's purpose and structure, explain its functionality and observed states, and anticipate future behaviours. Designers, who often possess intricate mental models of their own creations, may assume that every feature is intuitive and easy to grasp. However, users typically operate with more limited mental models, making them more prone to errors and perceiving the system as significantly more complex. The disparity between designers' and users' mental models frequently leads to usability challenges. By systematically identifying and bridging these gaps through evaluation, a truly user-centered ODE can be realized. Some open data portals have integrated web forms or specialized discussion forums in order to encourage communication among the various user communities. These forums allow users to share their experiences regarding how they have utilized the data that is made available through the open data portals. Due to the significant degree of variability that exists in this kind of user feedback, it is not possible to automatically compare the input that comes from different attempts (Aziz et al., 2022).

Beyond the state of the art: The increasing incorporation of artificial intelligence tools to enhance the usability of open data can play a crucial role in bridging misalignments between users' mental models and the complexity of datasets. AI-driven personalization can dynamically adapt open data portals to different expertise levels, offering tailored recommendations and adaptive interfaces. Additionally, cognitive feedback mechanisms, such as real-time clarifications and interactive tutorials, can help users navigate and interpret data more effectively. Conversational AI agents can further support understanding by providing dataset explanations, suggesting analytical approaches, and guiding users in their exploration. Moreover, AI-powered error detection can improve data quality by identifying inconsistencies, biases, or anomalies, increasing trust in open data sources. AI-generated data summarization techniques, whether textual or visual, can also facilitate mental model alignment, making complex datasets more accessible and actionable. By integrating these AI-driven solutions, ODEs can evolve into more user-centered environments, democratizing access and empowering a wider range of users to engage with data effectively.

5.2.8 Data exchange

Description: Data exchange methods, protocols, and standards can help in achieving open data sharing and interoperability among open data stakeholders. It can help in boosting the open data interoperability and maximizing its usage across the ODEs. Better data exchange reduces barriers

such as noise, duplication, and interoperability and makes possible cross-domain and cross-organization collaboration and supports the development of innovative applications. The challenges related to data exchange could be data in silos, inconsistent use of standards, and privacy and security concerns.

State of the art: State of the art in the open data exchange, revolves around the FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) principles and other open data standards, guidelines, and requirements adoption (Open Data Charter, 2013; Open Government Working Group, 2007). Some of the standards used such as DCAT (and custom metadata standards e.g. DCAT-AP), open API specifications-based interface designing, and other domain specific standards (OGC) are widely adopted to achieve the data exchange and interoperability of open data. Linked data principles and technologies (RDF, SPARQL, OWL) help in data linking and integration across open data amplifying open data machine readability and reuse (Abid & Laouar, 2018; Akatkin & Yasinovskaya, n.d.; Braga & Ribeiro Gouveia, 2022; Fayyaz et al., 2018). Open data tools like CKAN, DKAN, Socrata, OpenDataSoft, etc. are provide built in solution/plugins and customization option to achieve the tailored open data exchange (Ali et al., 2022a). Despite all these efforts, many challenges are still to be resolved, such as data fragmentation issues, data integration, cross-border open data interoperability, diverging quality of data, big data interoperability, data storage, and other semantic, legal, and organizational interoperability barriers (Abella et al., 2018; Ali et al., 2022b, 2024; Avgerinos Loutsaris et al., 2023).

Beyond the state of the art: The dynamic nature open data exchange requires beyond state-of-the-art intelligent and effective solutions and approaches integrated within current open data spaces. Artificial intelligence in this regard helps to resolve the semantic issues such as AI-driven data harmonization, compatibility checking, automated semantic annotation and metadata standards alignments, data integration, and linking. APIs and middleware solutions implementation are crucial to be integrated within open data portals to adapt to the highly dynamic nature of user needs in real time. Advances in cloud-edge computing can enable data processing and analysis within the portal boundary and beyond by enhancing the interoperability. Modern policies and software-based solutions for visualizing and monitoring data exchange, machine readability monitoring, automated compliance checks tools, interoperability validation tools, open data integration techniques, and integrated predictive analytics, along with co-development and stakeholder involvement, will boost the data exchange and overall interoperability of open data.

5.2.9 Data quality

Description: Data quality concerns the data's completeness, accuracy, consistency, timeliness, and availability, and the readily applied FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), but also data privacy and anonymization in the ODEs. High-quality data is essential for creating trust among stakeholders, achieving reliable and effective results and making decisions over this data, which further brings innovation. On the contrary, common barriers related to data quality, such as data not available in machine readable formats or not adhering to metadata standards (e.g., DCAT-AP), problems with incomplete, error-filled, and outdated datasets, and lack of metadata, can ultimately affect trust in open data available. Data quality assurance requires proper validation mechanisms, an effective standardization process per data domain, and maintaining the quality over time. These requirements are related to the ability of open data portals to provide users with functionalities such as improved search and results retrieval, data of improved quality, usage of technological means (such as data analysis tools, semantic technology, standards, linked data, data processing tools, anonymization techniques) in order to achieve and smoothen data integration, enhance the quality, and boost findability and contextual search (thus enabling semantic interoperability of data).

State of the art: The Open Data Maturity Report (Publications Office of the European Union, 2021) measures data maturity levels based on four open data dimensions: Policy, Impact, Portal and Quality. If one is to focus on the fourth dimension, quality, then the emphasis is put on quality matters on data but also its derived metadata. According to the Metadata Quality Assessment (MQA) methodology of the European Data Portal (European Commission, 2023), this is mainly focused on analysing whether format information is available, whether formats can be recognized (if they belong to internationally accepted lists of formats), and whether formats are machine-processable. A data quality assessment could include whether the data complies with the expected format, provide tools for the visualization of data in different formats, and provide tools for data analysis, integration, transformation, data scrubbing, and data fusion (data fusion is the process of integrating multiple data sources to produce more consistent, accurate, and useful information than that provided by any individual data source). In addition, data quality, dataset completeness, accuracy and transparency, data availability, legislation/policy, technical skills, and infrastructure (data exchange between governments and users, software for analysis, and platforms) are also mentioned by Safarov et al., (2017) as conditions for better use and re-use of OGD resources.

Beyond the state of the art: Beyond state-of-the-art approaches for data quality include the involvement of users to improve aspects of quality for available data. Schwoerer (2022) referred to data quality and how data can indeed be usable. Apart from the technical aspects of accessibility and navigation techniques, the ability of users to understand and interpret the information provided is put into focus (Schwoerer, 2022). An open data portal should provide the functionality of allowing the users to improve the quality of data (e.g., enrich metadata) if they discover the dataset lacks it, and there should be guidelines for the user to do it correctly. This way, users can contribute to data quality and improve the status of the datasets they are interested in using, making them more usable and discoverable to other users. In addition, open data portal administrators and data users must have the basic skills for data processing and for checking the quality of data. To achieve this, data quality, validity and completeness of the data may be evaluated with the use of technologies available via the data portal.

5.2.10 Collaboration and network effects

Description: Collaboration and network effects in ODEs emphasize decentralized peer-to-peer networks in operations and the formation of communities around shared interests (Briscoe and De Wilde, 2006) that come into action when diverse stakeholders want to communicate and generate value from shared data sources, goals and interests, policy- and governance-based coordination, among others. Collaboration and networking better implementation open doors to innovation, better decision-making, data reuse, and value (co-)creation. On the other hand, open data initiatives face challenges regarding lack of collaboration and network effects, which leads to a reduction in open data's envisioned benefits.

State of the art: Literature has found that effective collaboration in ODEs depends on governance structures, incentive mechanisms, and technological platforms that facilitate trust, standardization, and seamless data exchange (Mo et al., 2025; Runeson et al., 2021). Examples include open data cooperatives (Linåker & Runeson, 2020), federated data-sharing models (Casaletto et al., 2023), and API-driven platforms (Heshmatisafa & Seppänen, 2023), which enhance interoperability, access and reuse. However, collaboration in ODEs faces barriers such as data silos (Nikiforova et al., 2024), trust deficits (Linåker & Runeson, 2021), lack of common standards (Sugg, 2022), and proprietary constraints (Beno et al., 2017). Overcoming these challenges requires strong governance, economic incentives (Reggi & Dawes, 2022b), and global-local coordination mechanisms (López-Reyes et al., 2024) to realize the envisioned benefits of open data fully.

Beyond the state of the art: Research on local open government geodata has shown that collaboration across diverse stakeholders, including public authorities, businesses, and local communities, is essential for fostering inclusive decision-making and creating value from shared data (López-Reyes et al., 2024). Governance models that engage a wide range of actors, particularly at the local level, can enhance transparency and trust, thereby strengthening the collaboration necessary for ODEs to thrive. Future ODE designs must integrate multi-stakeholder governance models, such as data cooperatives or public data trusts, which could facilitate equitable participation by ensuring that control over data is distributed more evenly across diverse actors (Micheli et al., 2020). These governance structures can mitigate monopolization risks, supporting collaboration while addressing existing inequalities in data ownership and control. Integrating open technological platforms that allow for seamless data exchange across different stakeholders, enabling innovation, and cross-sector collaboration is key in ODEs (López-Reyes et al., 2024). Generative technologies such as APIs can facilitate the creation of new applications that support diverse use cases. As highlighted by Toorajipour et al. (2024) AIoT systems can significantly enhance the generative potential of ODEs by automating data processing and enabling real-time decision-making. However, while these technologies unlock vast opportunities, they also present technological barriers for smaller actors who lack the financial or technical resources to integrate such tools into their operations (i.e. local governments) (Zuiderwijk et al., 2018). Therefore, ODEs must not only provide the technological infrastructure needed for collaborative innovation but also support capacity-building initiatives to ensure that smaller entities, such as local businesses and NGOs, can engage fully. This can be achieved by offering shared infrastructures, subsidies, and training programs aimed at levelling the playing field and empowering underrepresented groups (Hambleton & Jeyaseelan, 2024).

There is also a need for trust-building mechanisms that consider the challenges stakeholders face in ODEs due to lack of transparency and unclear data ownership (López-Reyes et al., 2024). Establishing clear data governance structures that promote collaboration, and accountability is essential to overcoming these trust deficits, especially when local governments and citizens are engaged in data-sharing efforts. Trust remains a foundational element of successful ODEs, especially in light of increasing concerns over data privacy and security (Micheli et al., 2020). Current solutions, including blockchain and privacy-preserving technologies, have the potential to increase trust by ensuring transparency and accountability in data usage. However, concerns over selective openness, where only certain data sets are made accessible, continue to undermine the inclusivity of data-sharing initiatives (Beno et al., 2017). To address this, ODEs should implement clear data governance models that balance privacy with the need for openness.

Beyond economic incentives, the social value generated by ODEs is increasingly recognized as a key driver of sustainability. This underscores the importance of community-driven value creation where data is used not only for economic benefits but also to address social issues like urban governance (López-Reyes et al., 2024). Purpose-driven ODEs that focus on social inclusion and public services can contribute to addressing local needs while engaging citizens and fostering democratic participation (Verhulst et al., 2020).

The concept of purpose-driven data initiatives is gaining momentum, where data ecosystems are aligned with specific social and environmental goals. These initiatives, however, often face the challenge of balancing competing priorities among stakeholders. As businesses and governments prioritize innovation and profit, civil society and marginalized groups may emphasize transparency and equity (Sorri & Seppänen, 2021). A shift towards purpose-driven ODEs, guided by clear public-interest goals, will help align data practices with societal benefits, such as improving public health, fostering environmental sustainability, and promoting democratic engagement (Arena et al., 2022). Engaging underrepresented communities in decision-making processes through co-ownership or active partnerships will ensure that data initiatives reflect the collective needs of society.

One of the key challenges in sustaining the value of open data over time is the maintenance and curation of data, which requires ongoing investment (Jetzek et al., 2019). ODEs are not only about

the continuous generation of data but also about ensuring that data quality is preserved across its use, requiring proper infrastructure and feedback mechanisms to maintain long-term engagement (López-Reyes et al., 2024). Many ODEs rely on voluntary contributions from data providers, but without mechanisms to track data reuse and measure its value, contributors may lose incentives to continue sharing data (Lindman, 2014). To overcome this, ODEs must develop robust feedback systems that help measure the impact and value generation from shared data. Additionally, a balance must be struck between innovative data use and ensuring that data quality is maintained across all sectors (Tseng & Nikiforova, 2025).

5.2.11 Co-creation

Description: Open data co-creation is the process where multiple stakeholders take part, in a horizontal, user-centered way (Ansell & Torfing, 2021; Ochoa-Ortiz, 2023). It focuses on the shared contributions and collective impact of open data-driven initiatives. This might contain the development of tools, applications, and services to address the challenges (societal, economic, insufficient collaboration, limited stakeholder engagement) and create value for all involved actors. Enhancing value (co-) creation, impact, and innovation are essential for boosting the ODE potential.

State of the art: Traditionally, co-creation has been focused on citizen-government collaboration (McBride et al., 2018, 2019), but recent research emphasizes the need to engage the full quadruple helix —academia, industry, government, and society (Miller et al., 2018). Open data plays a key role in this process, yet its successful implementation depends on factors such as stakeholder motivation, proper communication, and technical infrastructure (McBride et al., 2019). While theoretical models for co-creation exist, practical implementations remain limited (Toots et al., 2017). Future developments should integrate standardized co-creation mechanisms into existing data platforms and address both technical and societal barriers to foster sustainable, value-creating ODEs.

Beyond the state of the art: Future considerations in co-creation should focus more on the inclusion of expanding stakeholder involvement, such as decentralized organizations and AI systems, which can enhance value co-creation through collaboration and innovation. The development and adoption of advanced co-creation frameworks tailored to diverse motivations, as well as the technical and social capabilities of stakeholder groups, will enable smoother collaboration. Enhancing co-creation practices on a global scale while addressing both technical and societal challenges, along with adopting AI for innovation, will contribute to more resilient and impactful ODEs. Real-time feedback interventions can drive innovation and adaptability, fostering ecosystem dynamics that sustain their relevance and impact.

5.2.12 Incentives

Description: Incentivizing ODE mechanisms that can motivate and stimulate the stakeholder's engagement and contributions. These incentives cover financial support, regulatory mandates, social benefits, and impacts. Incentives encourage stakeholders' involvement, data sharing, generating value, and bringing innovation in ODEs. The unavailability of incentive mechanisms limits the engagement and utilization of open data and available resources. Developing and aligning incentives are critical for sustaining open data stakeholders' participation and overall initiatives.

State of the art: The current incentives for the small-sized NPOs (Non-Profit Organisations) to engage and contribute to the ODE include achieving openness and transparency goals of the organizations and employees (Barnes et al., 2025). Openness is one of the values shared within the open data-focused NPOs as part of the cultivated and shared organisational culture of these organisations. NPOs aim to create a social impact as part of the cultivated and shared

organisational culture, which means they have an awareness about the social impact of open data sharing. Additionally, the organisational culture of NPOs is often less hierarchical, and employees can propose and take part in projects they enjoy, which means they have a presence of engagement or enjoyment activities to motivate data sharing. Another incentive is the community support and social impact of open data sharing and open data projects. It is motivating for small-sized NPOs to continue the project/data sharing, if the impact and support are evident, as their resources are otherwise limited, so they must prioritise which projects to work on/data to open.

Beyond the state of the art: For non-profit and non-governmental organizations, important incentives to open data sharing and value generation are training to improve data-literacy skills of the employees together with raising awareness of open data concepts. Smaller sized NPOs and NGOs may not have a dedicated programmer or skilled employee to share the data properly as open or reuse the existing open data to create social value. To motivate these actors, they need to have access to training and the ability to employ skilled employees. Another incentive for NPOs and NGOs is more financial cooperation that would support data-skilled employees and help NPOs run their open data projects long-term. There are existing examples of such cooperation, such as the Open Knowledge Foundation network's prototype fund, that can help small organisations or activists financially with their projects and data literacy training. A similar solution should be promoted, especially across the countries, to help distribute the resources to the NGOs with less support that needed for ODE engagement. Moreover, the creation of a common platform for NGOs to share the data, like open data government portals, could work as another incentive. The creation of such a portal could help with the availability of appropriate technical tools and availability of resources that many NGOs lack and, thus, are unable to share their data (Petti, 2024).

5.2.13 Value

Description: Well-organized open data initiatives generate values of different types, such as tangible and intangible values. These values can be growth in the economy, social awareness and empowerment, and sustainability in the field from which this open data is generated and shared. The value generation and its fair distribution is a long-standing discussion topic in open data.

State of the art: The current state of the art in value generation within ODEs showcases the balance between the autonomous, self-interested actors and the collaborative mechanisms that enable value creation. Davies (2011) emphasizes that successful value generation requires mobilizing a combination of technical, social, and political resources while fostering coordination and self-organization among ecosystem participants (Davies, 2011). Csáki (2019) further elaborates on ODEs as dynamic systems where actors and groups create shared meaning and value around open data, with their interactions shaping the ecosystem's growth and health (Csáki, 2019). Oliveira and Lóscio (2018) identify four core elements of an ODE—resources, roles, actors, and relationships—underscoring actor's flexibility in adopting various roles (Oliveira & Lóscio, 2018). Strategies for maximizing value are shifting from top-down interventions to community-driven approaches, recognizing the inadequacies of hierarchical models for handling multidirectional data flows.

Beyond the state of the art: While current research focuses on value creation in the ODE, there is a need to deepen the knowledge and understanding of value distribution mechanisms and their adaptability in the dynamic environment of an ODE. The development of value distribution algorithms in response to emerging stakeholder scenarios is crucial. Additionally, the creation of feedback loops and ecosystem health metrics can help facilitate value creation and fair distribution within the ODE. Furthermore, introducing new circular business models into the ODE and exploring how they can integrate with the circular economy and multi-stakeholder collaborations will contribute to more resilient and adaptable ODEs.

5.2.14 New concepts (AI4Data and Data4AI)

Description: Artificial intelligence may be considered as a driving force to drive the synergies in the field of open data. Its purpose is two-fold, firstly, using AI to improve the open data at various stages such as quality, metadata, alignment with standards. On the other hand, use of AI to develop applications and use-cases using open data to bring innovation and value-generation. AI4Data means improving open data in terms of quality (including also interoperability, integration, and metadata generation). Data4AI means using open data as a source and bringing AI analytical capabilities to foster innovation. Data4AI covers the aspects of making open data available for AI models training and testing. Advancement in AI4Data and Data4AI can open new opportunities in data-driven solutions or easy data product developments.

State of the art: Artificial Intelligence has revolutionized how open data is used, whether in data quality enhancements or innovative applications. The AI4Data paradigm focuses on enhancing open data at various stages, such as generating or improving metadata, enhancing data quality, making data interoperable, and standardizing it. Several studies have explored these topics, and they are still being investigated avidly following the advent of more advanced models. For instance, Ahmed et al., (2024) created a hybrid method (BRYT) combining conventional and advanced methodologies such as BERT, RAKE, YAKE, TextRank to extract keywords for open data sets. Song et al., (2024) utilize contemporary Large Language Models (LLMs) such as LLAMA and Mistral to extract metadata from more descriptive fields inside the dataset. Turgunbaev (2024) discusses various conventional machine learning methodologies for the particular use case of metadata extraction. Giglou et al., (2024) explore state of the art LLMs such as GPT, Llama, Mistral to perform ontology mapping ultimately as a use case for data interoperability. Bakker & Scala, (2024) perform ontology learning from textual data using contemporary LLM: GPT-4o. Alharbi et al., (n.d.) employ LLM- GPT to create an ontological structure – Knowledge Graph from medical texts. Maratsi et al., (2024) explore multiple ontologies and their possible interconnected mapping. Moreover, they employ GPT 3.5 and GPT 4 to generate the mappings and validate its accuracy on manual data.

Data4AI focuses on utilizing open data to enhance the development of AI applications. Open datasets provide significant opportunities for training and improving machine learning models. Access to high-quality open data speeds up AI research by lowering the costs and time required for data collection and preparation. Weber et al., (2024) emphasize the significance of open datasets for training machine learning models. They reflect the challenges associated with transparency, data access, and data curation, crucial for advancing open-source AI development. Arbeláez et al., (2024) underscore the significance of employing open data, which might be diverse and even unlabelled, as a better cost-effective alternative to custom-labelled data which might be expensive and might hinder development. Alam et al., (2023) highlight the role of open data and explainable AI in enhancing transparency, accountability, and interpretability in healthcare AI models. Employing diverse open data, the models can achieve better reliability and accuracy, promoting trust and openness.

State-of-the-art reflects how the synergy between AI4Data and Data4AI can create robust feedback loops. Improved data quality and metadata quality (AI4Data) lead to greater model performance, while AI applications and innovations (Data4AI) can further enhance data collection methods through the use of tools using AI. This dual advancement opens opportunities for new data-driven solutions, ranging from automated decision-making systems to scalable data products that address societal challenges.

Beyond the state of the art: The future holds significant potential for AI4Data and Data4AI. It would revolutionize data curation and AI model training. The current state particularly focuses on improving data quality, interoperability, and accessibility. Moving forward, we can also focus on self-optimizing dynamic ecosystems that use AI and reinforcement learning to maintain the integrity of data, metadata, and interoperability standards. From conventional static systems, it

would move to more dynamic systems that would be self-sufficient in addressing changing contexts and user needs. For instance, whatever data-related needs are communicated to the systems via LLMs, which understand the context of user needs, it would trigger the pertinent sub-model to address it and resolve it.

Moreover, data in ontological structure and knowledge graphs could prove to be a game changer for transparency, interoperability, and, ultimately, for training models. We could leverage the semantic capabilities of LLMs to build domain-specific ontologies to structure open data. It would highly enhance the interoperability and openness of the models that will be trained through those. The domain-specific ontologies and structure would highly enhance the AI model training for any particular domain task. Apart from being accurate it would turn out to be highly transparent and explainable in terms of its predictions. In the future, we may also see the emergence of AI-driven data marketplaces that facilitate the dynamic exchange and monetization of open data through blockchain-based platforms. These platforms would potentially enable data sharing by ensuring provenance, secure access, and fair compensation. This approach would significantly enhance data-driven innovation and promote economic growth on a global scale.

5.3 Towards a framework of an ODE

The framework and associated components require dedicated efforts to transform the open data realm and fill the gaps/problems by proposing specific strategies for mitigation. Eventually, by filling these gaps through the proposed strategies, a sustainable ODE framework can be formed. We have illustrated the ODE framework by first detailing the component-level aspects and exploring how each component can be theoretically enhanced through support from the literature and beyond state-of-the-art work. We then further extended this by analysing the interactions among the components themselves, aiming to make the ODE more user-driven, inclusive, circular, and skill-based. Figure 6 presents the resulting ODE framework outlining the components beyond their concepts including interactions and working within ODEs. Our ODE framework includes stakeholders, data, drivers, incentives, values, collaboration/network effect, co-creation, and open data infrastructure. Data quality and data exchange appear as possible driving forces in ODEs. Ahmed (2023) addresses challenges in data findability, accessibility, usability, and value creation through enhanced data quality. The literature also links these forces to evolving concepts that integrate artificial intelligence. Ahmed (2023) advocates using AI to overcome challenges in open data management—a notion in line with AI4Data—while Patel et al. (2023) emphasize data-centric innovations that exemplify Data4AI. Data quality and data exchange are key driving forces in ODEs, ensuring interoperability and usability, while AI4Data enhances data processing, and Data4AI relies on open data for training AI models (Ahmed, 2023; Ahmed et al., 2024; Kijanović et al., 2024). These components are integrated within the ODE framework. Each component of the ODE framework has been mapped to its corresponding drivers using different colours. Green boundaries represent user driven aspects, red indicates the circularity of the ODE framework, blue represents inclusiveness, and purple highlights skill-based components. In some cases, more than one driver corresponds to components.

The components of the ODE framework are very diverse in nature — encompassing entities (stakeholders), processes (data exchange and collaboration), intangible components (such as values and incentives), and technical elements (infrastructure). This diversity is intentional, as the framework aims to provide a holistic view of ODEs, where multiple dimensions — social, technical, institutional, and economic — interact and co-evolve. Rather than limiting the framework to one type of component, this inclusive approach captures the complexity and interconnectedness of real-world ODEs.

We conducted interactive workshops to reach the visualization of the ODE framework and associated components. The ODE framework was refined through these interactive workshops, discussions, and feedback within the consortium during the preparation of this deliverable.

Figure 6: A possible visualisation of an open data ecosystem framework

In Figure 6, we observe numerous interactions among diverse and multidisciplinary components, which raises concerns about the complexity, understandability, and straightforward application of the ODE framework. We have realized that this complex representation is difficult to grasp, indicating the need for further refinement — possibly by developing a less complex framework or breaking the overall framework into smaller, simpler sub-frameworks. This approach would help achieve better understanding of the ODE framework, its components, and the necessary support for ODE drivers. This idea will be considered as a future improvement to the ODE framework.

6 Analysis and Synthesis of Strategic Approaches

In this chapter, we present the analysis and synthesis of strategies for sustainable ODEs. We have collected 83 proposed strategies (see annex 1). We grouped and explained the proposed strategies based on their relationship with ODE Framework's components, and ODE drivers. Thorough analysis resulted in 29 distinct strategies; these 29 distinct strategies are listed in 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3 subheadings. These strategies foster the sustainability of an ODE. They reflect a wide range of multidisciplinary notions to be considered to design an ODE and further make it sustainable. In this chapter, we link the 29 unique strategies to the ODE drivers and present them accordingly (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Overarching strategies per ODE driver

6.1 Strategies towards a user driven open data ecosystem

Strategies pertaining to a user driven ODE include coordinated data stewardship between governmental and non-governmental actors, ensuring open data platforms incorporate user driven design, feedback mechanisms, and emerging technologies. Standardized interfaces, technical openness, and accessibility tools empower marginalized stakeholders and facilitate seamless data interaction. Institutional support, legal mandates, and funding policies strengthen sustainability, while open data events and needs assessments align data availability with societal and economic priorities. NGOs and industry collaborations enhance data usability, while tax incentives and funding models encourage sustained contributions. By fostering awareness of open data's social impact and aligning private interests with public value, participation and engagement in the ecosystem can be further expanded. Figure 8 illustrates the strategies (first degree) and additional approaches (second degree) for the sustainable ODE under the "user driven" driver.

Figure 8: User driven open data ecosystem strategies and additional approaches connected to a strategy

6.1.1 Coordinated data stewardship across governmental and non-governmental actors

The effective coordination of ODEs requires well-defined governance structures, typically managed by governmental actors. Governments play a crucial role in ensuring that data is collected, maintained, and shared in a way that maximizes its usability and societal impact. They set policies, establish standards, and ensure transparency, making ODEs more accessible and functional.

However, relying solely on government institutions to discharge these functions can lead to inefficiencies, bottlenecks, and scalability limitations. By introducing incentives, non-governmental actors—including private sector organizations, academic institutions, NGOs, and civic tech communities—can take on key roles in managing, improving, and disseminating open data. This distributed governance approach fosters a more dynamic, resilient, and sustainable circular data ecosystem where multiple actors collaborate to enhance data reusability, quality, and accessibility.

By allowing non-governmental actors to participate in open data governance with the right incentives—such as funding, recognition, data access privileges, or policy influence, the system benefits from diverse expertise, increased innovation, and a broader engagement base. This approach also ensures that data remains continuously updated, relevant, and applied to real-world challenges, reinforcing data circularity.

ODE's driver	User driven
ODE's framework components	Governance
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued implementation of legal mandates for open government data The public administration should institutionalize and support open data events Ensuring open data initiatives balance public and commercial interest Institutionalizing funding support policy support for open data infrastructure Enhancing coordination and efficiency in open data management Mandating open data usage and quality feedback in government agencies Cultivating strong organisational cultures oriented towards open data Developing a pipeline to engage the other open data providers as well.

6.1.2 Enhancing open data platforms

This strategy fosters enhancing open data platforms' interface and feedback mechanisms by adopting user driven design, making use of new technologies wherever this is possible, e.g., Natural Language Processing, Virtual and Augmented Reality, AI, and Chatbots. This strategy aims to improve usability, inclusivity, and engagement in open data portals by adopting user driven design principles and integrating advanced technologies. Natural Language Processing (NLP) and AI-powered chatbots can simplify dataset discovery and interaction, reducing barriers for non-technical users. Active feedback loops ensure continuous platform improvement by allowing diverse user groups including non-technical users to provide input and feedback on the data services. By fostering adaptive, intelligent, and inclusive open data portals, this strategy strengthens the user driven and inclusive dimensions of the ODE, improving both data accessibility and greater user engagement.

ODE's driver	User driven
ODE's framework components	Data provision, Enabling Environment, Infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community-centric design prioritizes the needs, preferences and involvement of communities in the ODE. By making resources (financial, time, people/workforce) available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged Introduce tools for unified data and physically impaired user groups.

6.1.3 Establish effective feedback mechanisms

Establishing effective feedback mechanisms strengthens the user driven and circular aspects of the ODE by enabling continuous data quality improvement, user engagement, and adaptive platform development. Feedback mechanisms such as feedback forms, dataset ratings, comments on the datasets, reporting issues related to the datasets, and discussion forums of the open data portals allow users to contribute insights and suggest enhancements. This fosters collaboration between data providers and users, ensuring that datasets remain relevant, accurate, and valuable for diverse stakeholders. Integrating structured feedback loops, such as user surveys, AI-driven sentiment analysis, and real-time engagement dashboards, enhance platform responsiveness and trust in open data services. Ultimately, this approach leads to a more dynamic, inclusive, and user-responsive ODE, facilitating greater adoption and impact across sectors.

ODE's driver	User driven
ODE's framework components	Data Usage
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating Needs Assessment and Communication in ODEs

6.1.4 Develop a standardized open data portal interface to make the data publication process easier

A standardized open data portal interface can streamline the data publication process by providing a user-friendly, consistent framework for data entry, metadata documentation, and access management. By establishing uniform guidelines for formatting, categorization, and tagging, such an interface reduces inconsistencies and ensures that datasets are easily discoverable and interoperable across different platforms. Additionally, automation features, such as built-in data validation and version control, can enhance data quality while minimizing the effort required from contributors. Open APIs and export functionalities further facilitate data sharing and integration with other analytical tools, maximizing the usability and impact of published datasets. Ultimately, a well-designed standardized interface simplifies the workflow for data providers, encourages broader participation, and enhances the accessibility and reliability of open data for researchers, policymakers, and the general public.

ODE's driver	User driven
ODE's framework components	Open data infrastructure

6.1.5 Technical openness of the datasets

By opening the datasets, it technically means to follow open standards, formats, and other protocols to enhance the data integration across different systems and to facilitate the better accessibility of the open data. Technical openness contributes to the technical interoperability of open data. This strategy can be put into action by bringing the technical openness of the open data to the portals and making the open data publication as per technical standards adopted. For example, as 5-star open data states that the higher the star, the more the data is machine-readable (or technically open), in this way, data accessibility and reuse can be maximized. Furthermore, providing access to all technical solutions (regarding choosing metadata, data formats, and comparing their benefits and disadvantages) can help in achieving openness by technical means possible.

Providing access to the open data through the means of REST APIs and following Open API specifications can also enhance the technical openness of open data. Providing open API explorer is a plus in the open data portal functionalities. Developing and utilizing the methodology to quantify the open data technical openness should be considered before making it online to the wider stakeholders.

ODE's driver	User driven
ODE's framework Components	Data Provision

6.1.6 Empowering marginalized stakeholders: encouraging inclusive participation in ODEs

Ensuring that less represented, less powerful, and disadvantaged actors have opportunities to provide feedback and actively contribute strengthens the inclusive and user driven dimensions of the ODE. Powerful organizations such as government agencies, large corporations, and regional institutions should proactively engage all diverse user groups, NGOs, and small-scale data contributors by creating accessible, multilingual, and low-barrier feedback channels. Providing incentives, training programs, and capacity-building initiatives can empower these groups to participate meaningfully. Additionally, adopting collaborative governance models, such as community-driven data stewardship and participatory policymaking, ensures that feedback is not only collected but also acted upon. By bridging power imbalances in data contribution and decision-making, this strategy enhances equity, diverse representation, and the long-term sustainability of ODEs.

ODE's driver	User driven
ODE's framework components	Governance
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open data events should be designed to be accessible by non-specialist users Aligning citizen needs and datasets for higher open data value not only in economic but also societal context NGOs' current and potential contributions can be in the form of different values that constitute social values, as these organisations cover a wide range of activities and exist as intermediaries rather than in end-user or producer only form. They are helping the users and the data provided by collaborating and addressing both and by adding value through these collaborations Leveraging tax incentives to support open data contributions (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organizations, and citizens) Incentivizing support for open data and open-source projects by training and support By aligning private value and interests with open data sharing, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged (e.g., ensuring that data

contributors—especially non-government actors—see tangible benefits from participating in ODE)

- By making stakeholders aware of the social impact of open data sharing, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged

6.2 Strategies towards an inclusive open data ecosystem

To achieve a sustainable ODE under the "Inclusive" driver, several strategies are emphasized. These include enabling multiple data access points, fostering collaboration among non-government data holders, and enhancing accessibility through user-friendly, multilingual design. Establishing shared goals, local problem-solving networks, and partnerships with industry players can further strengthen inclusivity. It also includes the implementation of FAIR and CARE principles, metadata repositories, open standards, and anonymization tools ensures usability while maintaining privacy and security. Legal frameworks, tax incentives, and public financing support infrastructure and long-term sustainability. Additionally, fostering awareness, supporting data intermediaries, and institutionalizing open data initiatives help drive adoption and engagement across diverse stakeholders. Figure 9 illustrates the strategies (first degree) and additional approaches (second degree) for the sustainable ODE under the "inclusive" driver.

Figure 9: Inclusive open data ecosystem strategies and additional approaches connected to a strategy

6.2.1 Enable multiple data access points

This strategy aims at (a) enabling diverse data formats and API options, and (b) building accessible user interfaces to enhance usability for non-technical users. Firstly, providing datasets not only through downloadable files but also through API endpoints would be an option for supporting a variety of formats. In this manner, conversion of datasets across formats would be easier programmatically, reducing the effort to download files and then feeding them into applications. Secondly, making data accessible through API endpoints and open data portal interfaces should be friendly for non-technical users too. This will make open data accessible for both technical and non-technical users.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	User Stakeholder's groups
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By making appropriate technical tools available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged • The FAIR Principles should be applied to achieve the user driven ODE. • Follow some kind of quality standards and data profiling techniques to achieve the user-needs regarding the data quality and usability.

- Use open standards, open formats available to engage the users with diverse needs. Some users require data in bulk, others require APIs, and others require Linked open data
- Use of open licenses should be encouraged

6.2.2 Facilitating data sharing among non-government data holders

This strategy aims at analysing the barriers, motivations, and technical requirements for non-government data holder groups to share their data and propose technical mechanisms to enable/facilitate this purpose. To analyse the barriers, motivations, and technical requirements for non-government data holder groups to share their data, it is essential to conduct a thorough examination of the specific challenges these groups face. Barriers may include concerns related to data privacy, security, intellectual property and other rights (e.g., personal data), and the potential for competitive disadvantages. Motivations for data sharing often stems from the desire to enhance innovation, foster collaboration, and gain access to public or academic research. Identifying these drivers can help create tailored solutions to overcome obstacles. Technical requirements for data sharing include ensuring interoperability, standardization of data formats, and the availability of secure and user-friendly platforms that facilitate seamless data exchange. It is also important to consider the scalability and sustainability of these technical solutions. To enable data sharing, propose mechanisms such as the development of open-source data platforms, the implementation of robust data anonymization techniques, the use of clear licensing frameworks, and the provision of incentives such as funding, recognition, or access to new markets. These mechanisms should be designed to ensure that data holders feel confident in sharing their data while maximizing the societal value of open data.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Enabling Environment
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partnerships can encourage non-government data holders to contribute open data, in addition to being users of open data. • Enhancing coordination and efficiency in open data management • Supporting and leveraging crowdsourced open data in Government Initiatives • Role of open data intermediaries in providing support for data supply and reuse • By making appropriate technical tools available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged • Implement metadata repositories • Provide documentation for metadata usability • Follow some kind of quality standards and data profiling techniques to achieve the user-needs regarding the data quality and usability • Use/develop tools to anonymize the open data

6.2.3 Building shared goals and values in an open data ecosystem

This strategy aims at creating shared goals and values among diverse stakeholders within an ODE. This ensures cohesive collaboration and maximizes the ecosystem's ability to deliver value across its users, contributors, and beneficiaries. To implement shared goals and values within an ODE, it is crucial to engage diverse stakeholders—such as government agencies, private sector entities, researchers, and citizens—early in the process. This can be achieved by organizing workshops, forums, or consultations to align a common vision, such as improving transparency, innovation, or social good. Clear communication of the ecosystem's objectives and mutual benefits fosters a collaborative culture where all participants understand their roles in data sharing, usage, and contribution.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Collaboration, Values
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By making data-sharing communities exist, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged

- Cultivating strong organizational cultures oriented towards open data
- Awareness is needed in the socio-technical conditions in which interactions between actors take place
- Introduce tools for unified data and physically impaired user groups
- Seek guidance and infrastructure from the already developed portals from other countries, areas, and regions to develop your one
- Actors should be knowledgeable of the purposes and practices that can be affected through open data

6.2.4 Improving open data accessibility through user-friendly and multilingual design

This strategy aims at simplifying interfaces with user-friendly designs and incorporate multilingual support and accessibility features. To maximize inclusivity and engagement in ODEs, platforms should prioritize user-friendly design, multilingual support, and accessibility. Simplifying interfaces with intuitive layouts, interactive visualizations, and no-code tools can make data more accessible to both experts and non-experts. Providing multilingual support through localized interfaces, dataset translations, and natural language search capabilities ensures broader participation, especially for global and transnational issues. Additionally, incorporating accessibility features such as screen reader compatibility, keyboard navigation, high-contrast visuals, and alternative data formats enables individuals with disabilities to effectively interact with open data. By integrating these elements, open data platforms can foster more equitable access, enhance usability, and empower diverse communities to engage with and benefit from open data initiatives.

Drivers	Inclusive
Framework	Collaboration, Value (co) creation, network effect
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandating open data usage and quality feedback in government agencies • The data should be findable to a wide range of users with diverse search options • Different disabilities should be taken into account and addressed from design requirements

6.2.5 Scoping local problems and building collaborative networks for open data solutions

To effectively scope local problems and build networks of actors with open data (OD) flows, it is essential to conduct a comprehensive needs assessment to identify context-specific challenges that can be addressed through open data solutions. This process involves engaging a diverse array of local stakeholders, such as governmental bodies, private sector entities, academic institutions, and civil society organizations, to collaboratively define the data requirements and potential applications for resolving identified issues. By mapping out these challenges and opportunities, a local ODE can be established, facilitating the exchange of open data and expertise across sectors. The establishment of a shared digital infrastructure, such as open data platforms, is crucial to ensuring the seamless flow of information among actors, thereby enabling data-driven decision-making. Furthermore, capacity-building initiatives should be implemented to enhance the data literacy of local stakeholders, empowering them to effectively engage with and utilize open data in addressing community-specific problems. To sustain these efforts, regular forums or workshops should be organized to maintain an ongoing dialogue, ensuring that the collaborative network remains adaptive and responsive to evolving local needs and priorities.

Drivers	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide tools for local data interpretation • Create community-specific manuals and localized data insights platforms • Key enablers to contribute data to the ODE were identified, that relate to the motivations and barriers found by users • By making data-sharing communities exist, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged

6.2.6 Strategies for facilitating collaboration between domain experts and data experts

To apply strategies that incentivize and facilitate collaboration between domain experts and data experts, start by creating structured opportunities for interaction, such as cross-disciplinary workshops, hackathons, or collaborative research projects. These events can help both groups understand each other's language, challenges, and goals, fostering mutual respect and knowledge exchange. Offer incentives like funding, grants, or recognition to encourage domain experts to actively engage with data experts, emphasizing the value of their expertise in unlocking new insights and solutions. Additionally, establish clear channels for ongoing communication and collaboration, such as shared platforms or forums, where both types of experts can regularly contribute and access each other's work. Provide training and capacity-building programs to help domain experts gain basic data skills, and data experts to understand the nuances of specific domains, ensuring they can effectively collaborate. Lastly, showcase successful collaborative projects to demonstrate the value of cross-disciplinary partnerships, reinforcing the benefits of cooperation in advancing innovation and solving complex problems.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Enabling Environment
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key enablers to contribute data to the ODE were identified, that relate to the motivations and barriers found by users • Collaborating with industry players to showcase open data potential • ODE should facilitate the integration of open data from cross-domains (either government, non-government, NGOs)

6.2.7 Adopting thematic classification of datasets from European Data Portal (EDP)

The adoption of thematic classification of datasets will enhance the findability, accessibility, and interoperability of open datasets through open data portals. By categorizing and correctly classifying the theme of the datasets, users can more easily locate and find the relevant datasets, and this can improve the usability of the open data portal for researchers, businesses, and policymakers. This strategy strengthens the inclusive and user driven aspects of the ODE.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Data Provision

6.2.8 Practical implementation of CARE and FAIR principles in open data legal frameworks

In terms of practical implementation, legal frameworks for open data initiatives could refer to CARE principles in addition to the FAIR principles for data quality management (Di Staso et al., 2023). These CARE Principles do not focus only on inherent qualities of data that enable more sharing and re-use but also focus on power differentials. As a result, CARE Principles also focus on realising collective benefit from open datasets, as well as ensuring commitment to ethics. (Carroll et al., 2020). There are examples of CARE principles being translated into the design and implementation of open data initiatives - such as the Open Data Mekong project. (Chung & Chung, 2019; DCPC, 2024).

To implement legal frameworks incorporating both the FAIR and CARE principles, a multi-layered approach is essential to ensure data quality, accessibility, and ethics. FAIR principles should be integrated into policies mandating standardized metadata and creating platforms that support data interoperability across sectors. At the same time, CARE principles must address power dynamics and ensure ethical data practices. This can be achieved through governance mechanisms involving local communities, ensuring they have control over their data and are part of decision-making processes, like the Open Data Mekong project.

Practically, data stewardship agreements can be developed, outlining data access terms and respecting community rights. Data impact assessments should evaluate how data use affects vulnerable groups, ensuring ethical sharing practices. Additionally, legal frameworks should

provide resources and training for stakeholders to operationalize these principles and foster continuous public engagement to maximize collective benefits from open data.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	ODE
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued implementation of legal mandates for open government data Enhance data licensing and anonymisation by employing technological facilitators to achieve this purpose, such as Machine Learning, data encryption, GenAI and legal interoperability facilitators The FAIR Principles should be applied to achieve the user driven ODE

6.2.9 Establishing and implementing a national or supra-national consortium for open data sharing

To implement a national or supra-national consortium for open data sharing by non-public organizations, first, identify key stakeholders across the public, private, and civil sectors, ensuring representation from diverse areas such as technology, academia, business, and civil society. Establish a governance framework with a steering committee that includes representatives from these sectors to facilitate decision-making on both technical (e.g., infrastructure, standards) and non-technical (e.g., policies, legal considerations) issues. The consortium should collaboratively define goals, such as ensuring data accessibility, interoperability, and sustainability. Develop a shared, non-proprietary technical infrastructure (e.g., open-source platforms, APIs, data repositories) that is easy to adopt and scale. Secure joint financial backing through agreements with consortium members, ensuring sustainable funding through contributions, grants, or revenue-sharing models. Regularly evaluate the consortium's activities to maintain alignment with stakeholders' evolving needs and priorities, fostering continuous collaboration and improvement in the ecosystem.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Open data infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continued implementation of legal mandates for open government data Public financing and maintenance of shared open infrastructures, like the European Open Science Cloud The public administration should institutionalize and support open data events Institutionalizing funding support policy support for open data infrastructure Leveraging tax incentives to support open data contributions Willingness on part of public administrations to engage in formal and informal partnerships with other civic actor groups Seek guidance and infrastructure from the already developed portals from other countries, areas, regions to develop your one

6.2.10 Thematical annotation of open data

Open data portals publish data by annotating the data with the domain or theme that the data possibly belongs to base on the data provider's suggestion or metadata information. EDP provides a thematic annotation schema for the incoming datasets from the member states. UN sustainable development goals could be another possible categorization by using which open data can be thematically annotated. Following multiple themes for the data can also serve the cross-domain and cross-theme, increasing the data's findability and semantic interoperability of the open data.

ODE's driver	Inclusive
ODE's framework components	Data Provision
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use/develop tools to anonymize the open data

6.2.11 Intermediation in providing tools for diverse datasets for data augmentation and quality enhancement

This strategy aims at 1. creating and distributing data augmentation tools adaptable to different dataset types, and 2. developing tools capable of supporting a wide variety of data types and intended uses. Intermediaries can create and distribute adaptable data augmentation and validation tools for diverse data types. The data validation and augmentation tool functionalities may provide a way to enhance the open data quality.

ODE's driver	Skill-based
ODE's framework components	Intermediaries
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt open standards for datasets • Implement metadata validation tools for consistent data quality

6.2.12 Low-code tools provision for data analysis

Create and distribute low-code tools for data analysis. Offer training to educators and intermediaries on using these platforms. By keeping in view, the expertise spectrum of open data stakeholders to draw the information, knowledge, and wisdom from the data. Low-code data analytics tools can help in the understanding of the open data and further generate insights from the open data.

ODE's driver	Skill-based
ODE's framework components	Data usage

6.3 Strategies towards a circular ODE

To achieve a circular ODE, strategies focus on resource provision, stakeholder collaboration, and infrastructure development. Training in data literacy, dataset linking, and metadata validation ensures quality and integration across domains. Partnerships with industry, public financing, and incubators sustain open data intermediaries and community-driven initiatives. Leveraging AI and machine learning improves metadata annotation, interoperability, and data compliance. Encouraging open licenses, and aligning public-private interests ensure long-term sustainability while balancing economic and societal values. Figure 10 illustrates the strategies (first degree) and additional approaches (second degree) for the sustainable ODE under the "circular" driver.

Figure 10: Circular open data ecosystem strategies and additional approaches connected to a strategy

6.3.1 Resource provision and support for small sized NGOs

For small sized NGOs to be able to share their data as open and pursue open data projects, they, firstly, need to be aware of open data concepts and have data literacy on a certain level. Secondly, to have training or hire a data specialist, and to support data sharing and other open data related activities NGOs need to have financial resources that they can allocate to that. Moreover, infrastructure for open data sharing might be expensive and hard to maintain for a small sized NGO, thus resources are also needed for that. Some NGOs have an interest in the creation of a common platform specific to them, similar to the government data platforms, where they could share their open data. Overall, the small sized NGOs need stable resources support from other stakeholders in the ecosystem to be more equipped to share their open data and run the open data projects.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Governance
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public financing and maintenance of shared open infrastructures, like the European Open Science Cloud Supporting open-source software development By making resources (financial, time, people/workforce) available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged Developing a pipeline to engage the other open data providers as well Facilitating needs assessment and communication in ODEs

6.3.2 Bridging stakeholders through boundary objects

Boundary objects are essential for fostering inclusivity, enhancing collaboration, and bridging gaps between stakeholders such as governments, NGOs, businesses, and individual citizens. Boundary objects are artifacts—such as datasets, standards, dashboards, maps, or frameworks—that facilitate communication and collaboration across different stakeholder groups. In the context of ODEs, they serve as shared references that help align diverse perspectives and promote open data reusability, ultimately enhancing the circularity of open data. Boundary objects can foster inclusivity, as they enable stakeholders with varying levels of expertise and interests to interact with open data in a meaningful way. For instance, policymakers and community activists may interpret datasets differently, but well-structured boundary objects can create common ground, enabling productive discussions and joint problem-solving. By acting as a bridge, boundary objects help overcome the technical, semantic, and organizational barriers that often hinder data sharing and collaboration. They encourage interoperability, facilitate the co-creation of knowledge, and support the sustainable use of open data resources.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partnerships can encourage non-government data holders to contribute open data, in addition to being users of open data Provide training on dataset linking and blending tools Enable version control for community-shared datasets NGOs' current and potential contributions can be in the form of different values that constitute social values, as these organizations cover a wide range of activities and exist as intermediaries rather than in end-user or producer only form. They are helping the users and the data provided by collaborating and addressing both and by adding value through these collaborations Supporting and leveraging crowdsourced open data in government initiatives Collaborating with industry players to showcase open data potential Fostering collaboration through initiatives led by open data intermediaries Supporting open data intermediaries' business models through incubators Willingness on part of public administrations to engage in formal and informal partnerships with other civic actor groups

- ODE should facilitate the integration of open data from cross-domains (either government, non-government, NGOs)

6.3.3 Knowledge hubs for open data infrastructure and expertise exchange

This strategy aims at designing open data infrastructures as a hub for creativity, learning, exploration, and knowledge sharing. Open data infrastructures should be designed as dynamic hubs that foster creativity, learning, exploration, and knowledge sharing by providing intuitive tools, collaborative spaces, and diverse data resources. By integrating interactive dashboards, customizable APIs, and open-source tools, these platforms can empower users to experiment with data, develop innovative applications, and generate new insights. Educational resources such as tutorials, case studies, and data literacy programs can support users at different skill levels, transforming these infrastructures into learning ecosystems. Additionally, fostering collaboration through forums, data challenges, and open research initiatives encourages knowledge exchange and collective problem-solving. By serving as interconnected spaces for innovation and discovery, open data hubs can drive impactful solutions and democratize access to data-driven insights.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public financing and maintenance of shared open infrastructures, like the European Open Science Cloud • Provide training on dataset linking and blending tools • Enable version control for community-shared datasets. • Role of open data intermediaries in providing support for data supply and reuse • Fostering collaboration through initiatives led by open data intermediaries • Supporting open data intermediaries' business models through incubators • Open data community portal development helps in the identification of issues with data, the possible use of data, and future improvements • Awareness is needed on the socio-technical conditions in which interactions between actors take place • Actors should be knowledgeable of the purposes and practices that can be affected through open data

6.3.4 Unlocking open data potential through value creation and networked interactions

Focus on value creation and potential contributions show a rich network of roles and interactions. A sustainable and dynamic ODE thrives when stakeholders recognize not just the availability of data, but also the value they can generate from it and the roles they can play within the system. This strategy emphasizes value creation and potential contributions by showcasing the extensive network of interactions among governments, businesses, researchers, civil society, and individual users. Instead of viewing open data merely as a resource for passive consumption, this approach encourages stakeholders to actively engage in data generation, refinement, analysis, and reuse. As data flows through various hands and across sectors, it gathers additional insights, enhancements, and applications, ensuring its usefulness is maximized over time—this embodies the essence of data circularity. By mapping out a network of roles and interactions, stakeholders can gain a clearer understanding of their place in the ecosystem, how they can contribute, and how they can benefit from collaborating with others. This fosters a more interconnected and sustainable system where data is continuously enriched, repurposed, and utilized for innovation.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By making stakeholders aware of the social impact of open data sharing, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged

6.3.5 Designing interactive and adaptive visualizations for dynamic ODEs

Visualizing ODEs as multi-layer networks provides a useful framework for understanding the complex interactions among actors, data flows, and governance structures. However, for such visualizations to be effective, it is critical to first define distinct layers—such as data providers, platforms, users, and legal frameworks—and identify relevant stakeholders, including government, private sector, and civil society entities. These relationships, encompassing data sharing, policy development, and collaborations, can be mapped using network techniques from graph theory, which allows the visualization of data flows and the identification of centralized or decentralized elements within the ecosystem.

The use of advanced data visualization tools like D3.js, Gephi, or Cytoscape enhances interactivity by allowing users to explore the ecosystem through zooming, filtering, and drilling down into layers. While these dynamic features promote deeper engagement, they also introduce the risk of oversimplification or confusion if not carefully structured. Additionally, ensuring that these visualizations are linked to real-time data sources via APIs presents challenges related to data accuracy and consistency, as the ecosystem must continuously evolve to account for new data sources and stakeholders.

Incorporating user feedback mechanisms—such as annotations, voting, or suggestions—can promote sustained engagement, but the process may introduce biases if not carefully moderated. The integration of machine learning for predictive insights may further complicate the interpretation of trends if the underlying algorithms are not transparent or if they privilege certain data patterns over others. Ultimately, while combining multi-layer network mapping with interactivity and real-time updates holds significant potential for managing ODEs, the design and implementation of such visualizations must carefully address challenges related to data accuracy, user engagement, and algorithmic transparency to avoid misrepresentation or overinterpretation.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to build skillset in the field of data visualisation and build capacity regarding data issues (fragmentation, aggregated data, unreliable data, and sensitive data)

6.3.6 Employing open data standards and formats

The Open Data Platform (ODP) requires backing for data integration and interoperability from a range of stakeholders, including governmental and non-governmental entities. Employing open data standards and formats can streamline data accessibility and sharing within ODEs, enhancing their circularity.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Resources, open data infrastructure, Data Provider
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt open standards for datasets • Implement metadata validation tools for consistent data quality • Enhance the data creation process by employing several technical mechanisms and technologies to improve critical aspects of data creation, quality and integration, such as augmenting semantic interoperability with the help of Large Language Models to automate or semi-automate processes that improve it, improving metadata annotation in open data portals using AI, or validating/checking technical compliance of data on the web • The data should be findable to a wide range of users with diverse search options • Need to build skillset in the field of data visualisation and build capacity regarding data issues (fragmentation, aggregated data, unreliable data, and sensitive data) • Open data community portal development helps in the identification of issues with data, the possible use of data, and future improvements. • Focus should be put on - different types of - interoperability and data portability

- Open data intermediaries could consider providing an open data platform based on federated architecture

6.3.7 Adopting scalable infrastructure technologies

As the amount of data is increasing in various ways, managing and providing smooth access and other operations (querying, filtering, downloading, etc.) on a large scale require an underlying infrastructure with scalability in terms of memory and processing. Big data and cloud-based technologies are good options. Instead of storing large amounts of data on premises, adopting cloud infrastructure is a viable alternative. A hybrid approach (combining on-premises and cloud infrastructure) can also be considered.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Resources, open data infrastructure, Data Provider
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public financing and maintenance of shared open infrastructures, like the European Open Science Cloud • Enhance the data creation process by employing several technical mechanisms and technologies to improve critical aspects of data creation, quality and integration, such as augmenting semantic interoperability with the help of Large Language Models to automate or semi-automate processes that improve it, improving metadata annotation in open data portals using AI, or validating/checking technical compliance of data on the web • Enhance data licensing and anonymization by employing technological facilitators to achieve this purpose, such as Machine Learning, data encryption, GenAI and legal interoperability facilitators. • Supporting open-source software development • Implement metadata repositories • Provide documentation for metadata usability • Use of open licenses should be encouraged • To ensure sustainability of ODEs, different types of funding models should be considered • Open data intermediaries could consider providing an open data platform based on federated architecture

6.3.8 Assessing the implementation of interactive visualization tools for data exploration and comprehension

The implementation of interactive visualization tools for data exploration requires careful evaluation to ensure they address both user needs and data complexities. While platforms like, Plotly, and Tableau and library like D3.js enable dynamic interaction with datasets, there is a risk of oversimplification or information overload. Excessive options may overwhelm users, while customization features—such as colour choices—can distort data interpretations if not carefully managed. Ensuring that visualizations balance flexibility with clarity is crucial to prevent misinterpretation.

Moreover, interactive features can introduce confirmation bias, where users manipulate the data to confirm preconceived beliefs rather than explore it objectively. Contextual guidance, such as explanatory annotations, is essential to help users understand data limitations. Real-time data integration is beneficial but comes with challenges regarding accuracy and consistency, as delays or inconsistencies could affect the reliability of the tool.

While inclusivity features, like colour-blind-friendly palettes and screen-reader compatibility, are important, they often limit design flexibility. Additionally, real-time collaboration can raise concerns about data privacy, particularly in sensitive environments. Feedback loops for refining tools are important but can be biased by the most vocal users, highlighting the need for evidence-based iterations driven by data-driven insights. In conclusion, interactive visualization tools have great potential, but their design must address issues of accessibility, data integrity, and user behaviour to provide meaningful, reliable insights while avoiding misrepresentation.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	open data infrastructure

6.3.9 Maximizing open data utilization through a purpose driven approach

In many ODEs, the traditional approach is user driven, where the primary focus is on enabling access to data and letting users define its applications. While this fosters broad engagement, it can also lead to fragmented, inefficient, or even unintended uses of data, with varying levels of impact.

A purpose-driven approach, in contrast, prioritizes clear societal goals as the guiding principle for data publication, management, and reuse. Rather than merely making data available and hoping it finds useful applications, this model proactively aligns open data initiatives with pressing societal challenges—such as climate action, public health, urban resilience, and social equity.

By embedding purpose and social value into the core of ODEs, stakeholders—including governments, businesses, researchers, and civil society—can ensure that data-driven initiatives lead to meaningful, measurable, and responsible outcomes. This approach also encourages ethical considerations, prevents data misuse, and fosters sustainable long-term engagement in the data ecosystem.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	ODE
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligning citizen needs and datasets for higher open data value not only in economic but also societal context Ensuring open data initiatives balance public and commercial interests By aligning private value and interests with open data sharing, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged Use open standards, open formats available to engage the users with diverse needs. Some users require data in bulk, others require APIs, and others require Linked open data Focus should be put on - different types of - interoperability and data portability

6.3.10 Make training in data skills and literacy available

In media organizations, the lack of skills is prominent, although the gap has been identified both by media organizations and academics in the journalism sector. University programs in journalism now include data journalism as a topic in their curriculum, and several workshops and online training opportunities exist for journalists to acquire initial data skills that they can apply in their work. While younger journalists are more exposed through their studies, tools and opportunities also exist for more senior professionals to develop these skills.

ODE's driver	Circular
ODE's framework components	Incentives
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open data events should be designed to be accessible by non-specialist users

6.3.11 Adaptive engagement strategies

ODEs thrive when stakeholders actively contribute, access, and reuse data. However, a one-size-fits-all approach to engagement often falls short in addressing the diverse needs, incentives, and capabilities of different actors, including governments, businesses, researchers, non-profits, and local communities.

Adaptive engagement strategies emphasize flexibility and customization in how stakeholders interact with open data. Rather than relying on static outreach methods or rigid policies, adaptive engagement involves continuously evolving strategies to accommodate changing user needs, technological advancements, and societal priorities. This ensures that engagement remains relevant, dynamic, and inclusive.

By employing data-driven insights, feedback loops, and iterative engagement models, this strategy fosters sustained participation, trust, and value creation in the ODE. Adaptive engagement is key to data circularity, as it ensures that data is continuously updated, refined, and applied across different use cases, maximizing its lifecycle and impact.

ODE Drivers	Circular
ODE's framework components	Incentives
Additional approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentivizing support for open data and open-source projects • To ensure sustainability of ODEs, different types of funding models should be considered

6.4 Integration of all strategies to the ODE framework clickable version

Figure 11 is a screenshot of the developed clickable version to easily navigate through the ODE framework, drivers, and corresponding strategies per ODE framework's components. The second level of the information, after clicking intermediaries can be seen in Figure, it lists all the key elements per drivers, and strategies to include/fulfil these strategies per drivers have been popped up on the screen. In a similar way, users can navigate through the ODE framework's components and their relationship with ODE drivers, key-elements, and strategies. A clickable version is available online through the GitHub repository⁴.

The ODE Framework provides a practical, holistic guide for ODE initiators to design, evaluate, and strengthen their initiatives. By clearly outlining key components—such as stakeholders, data flows, governance, infrastructure, and driving forces—the framework helps users understand how these elements interact and co-evolve. The clickable online version allows initiators to explore each component in detail, supported by strategies drawn from workshops and research. This enables them to identify gaps, apply best practices, and tailor strategies—such as promoting user drivenness, ensuring data quality, and fostering inclusive collaboration—to build sustainable and impactful ODEs.

For example, if the Greek government is considering the development of a national ODE, the ODE Framework could serve as a valuable foundational tool to structure and guide their efforts. By offering a comprehensive view of essential components—such as stakeholders (ministries, agencies, citizens, private sector), data provision and usage, governance models, and technical infrastructure—the framework provides a clear roadmap for action. Using the clickable online version, government officials could explore each component in greater depth, supported by practical strategies and examples. For instance, they could focus on engaging citizens through user driven initiatives, enhancing data quality and accessibility, and fostering collaboration between public and private sectors. The framework also highlights key drivers like inclusiveness and circularity, which could inform policy decisions and promote long-term sustainability. By adopting the ODE Framework, the Greek government would be well-positioned to take a strategic, informed, and holistic approach to building a robust, future-ready ODE.

⁴ <https://mohsanaliac.github.io/OpenDataEcosystemFramework/>

Figure 11: Screenshot of the clickable version developed to easily navigate in the open data ecosystem framework, drivers and corresponding strategies

Intermediaries

- 1. Key elements identified**
 - 1.1. Inclusive**
 - 1.1.1.
 - 1.2. Circular**
 - 1.2.1. Value (co-)creation by the ODE actors: Understanding potential contributions of open government data users to the open data ecosystem.
 - 1.2.2. Various open data intermediation value propositions addressing various real-world challenges and providing innovative solutions.
 - 1.2.3. Advisory, consultancy or support services to existing or potential open data actors.
 - 1.2.4. Initiating engagement and interaction among open data actors
 - 1.2.5. The availability of open source software for open data supply, processing, and reuse.
 - 1.2.6. Sustainable business models for open data intermediaries.
 - 1.2.7. Fiscal incentives in exchange for contributions to open data initiatives.
 - 1.3. user-driven**
 - 1.3.1. The availability of open data platform based on federated architecture.
 - 1.3.2. Soliciting various needs of existing and potential open data actors.
 - 1.4. Skill-based**
 - 1.4.1. Providing assistance to data intermediaries to improve the quality of data: The use of methods/approaches that increase data quality, such as validation and augmentation, is crucial in order to make open datasets better and to ensure that they are accessible to all different kinds of users simultaneously.
- 2. Key Strategies proposed**
 - 2.1. Inclusive**
 - 2.1.1.
 - 2.2. Circular**
 - 2.2.1. NGOs as Value-Adding Intermediaries: NGOs' current and potential contributions can be in the form of different values that constitute social use values, as these organisations cover a wide range of activities and exist as intermediaries rather than in end-user or producer only form. They are helping the users and the data provider by collaborating and addressing both of them and by adding value through these collaborations."
 - 2.2.2. Open data advocates (such as open data NGOs, researchers, and public agencies) could engage with domain-specific industry players (such as mobility, agriculture, energy sectors) to showcase the potential use of open data and exemplary value-added services.
 - 2.2.3. Open data intermediaries (within or outside public sector) should consider introducing functions to provide technical and non-technical supports to other open data actors in supplying, processing, and reusing open data.
 - 2.2.4. Beyond holding events such as hackathons or conferences that bring various actors in one place to connect, open data intermediaries may also consider initiating or leading collaborative initiatives that harness the resources and expertise of multiple open data actors.
 - 2.2.5. The development of open source software should be supported, especially by providing funds for open source software development and maintenance.
 - 2.2.6. Incubator or similar programs to support the design and development of open data intermediaries' business models could be initiated to help existing and future open data intermediaries. These programs could be catered not only to for-profit but also non-profit open data intermediaries, as the former also requires sustainable business models.
 - 2.2.7. Governments should consider offering financial incentives to citizens and companies that support open data or open source projects.

Figure 12: Clicking intermediaries on the open data ecosystem framework, popups a full list of key elements per drivers, and strategies per drivers.

7 Recommendations

This final section aims at proposing recommendations for institutions and actors producing, using or otherwise contributing to the ODE, to be implemented in order to support sustainable ODEs. The 29 strategies led to the creation of 11 recommendations in technical and governance categories. These 11 recommendations may improve usability and accessibility, quality, and participation through a set of 5 technical and 6 governance strategies. They were designed to be scalable and to enable them to make a difference with limited budgets.

To sustain the ecosystem, the facilitation of open data sharing among non-government data holders is crucial. Encouraging private entities, research institutions, and civil society organizations to share data requires addressing legal, technical, and organizational barriers. Establishing clear licensing frameworks, anonymization techniques, and secure open data-sharing mechanisms can help build trust among non-government data holders. Open-source platforms can further support seamless collaboration by ensuring interoperability and compliance with existing data standards. Partnerships and coordination efforts should also be strengthened to promote contributions from diverse stakeholders.

7.1 Technical recommendations

7.1.1 Improve discoverability by adopting thematic structured classification models

Standardizing the classification of datasets ensures consistency and improves data discoverability. Adopting established classification frameworks, such as those used by the European Data Portal, facilitates interoperability and alignment with broader data ecosystems. Thematic categorization enhances the usability of datasets, enabling more efficient search, retrieval, and analysis by end users. Moreover, enhancing metadata quality for improved data discoverability to maximize the impact of open data, policymakers should enforce rigorous metadata requirements, ensuring datasets include comprehensive descriptions, provenance, and structured classifications. This will improve data discoverability, support machine-readable formats, and enable more effective data utilization by researchers, businesses, and the public sector.

7.1.2 Promoting standardization through linked open data for semantic interoperability

Governments should prioritize the adoption of Linked Open Data principles to strengthen semantic interoperability. By leveraging ontologies such as SKOS and Wikidata, data portals can interlink datasets more effectively, allowing for better contextualization, cross-domain analysis, and enhanced knowledge extraction. Governments and organizations should establish mandatory compliance with widely accepted interoperability standards such as DCAT, FOAF, and Schema.org. Ensuring adherence to these standards will facilitate seamless data exchange across platforms, enhance data usability, and promote a more integrated ODE. This will strengthen open data Interoperability Through Standardization.

7.1.3 Establishing effective feedback mechanisms for ODE improvement

To enhance user engagement and data quality, the establishment of feedback mechanisms such as user surveys, dataset ratings, and discussion forums on open data platforms should be included. These tools allow users to report issues, suggest improvements, and engage in continuous dialogue with data providers. Integrating AI-driven sentiment analysis and real-time dashboards can help improve platform responsiveness and trust, creating a dynamic and user-responsive ecosystem that fosters continuous data quality improvement and broader adoption.

7.1.4 Standardizing open data portal interfaces to simplify data publication

Governments should adopt standardized interfaces for open data portals that streamline the data publication process. A uniform framework for data entry, metadata documentation, and access management will reduce inconsistencies and ensure datasets are discoverable and interoperable

across platforms. Automation tools like data validation and version control can enhance data quality, while open APIs and export functionalities will maximize data sharing and integration, ultimately improving accessibility and encouraging broader participation in the ODE.

7.1.5 Improve technical usability and openness

Enhancing data usability requires offering diverse access points, including various data formats, APIs, and user-friendly interfaces that accommodate both technical and non-technical users. Applying FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, open standards, and data quality profiling techniques ensures greater accessibility and engagement. By enabling multiple entry points, users can retrieve and interact with data more efficiently, fostering broader adoption and utilization of open data. Policymakers should encourage the adoption of technical openness in data publication by adhering to machine-readable formats, following Open API specifications, and utilizing technical standards that improve data integration across systems. Offering tools such as API explorers and fostering collaboration on technical solutions will ensure that datasets are accessible and reusable. A methodology to quantify the technical openness of datasets should be developed to ensure that open data platforms meet the highest standards of data interoperability. Ensuring inclusivity in open data platforms involves designing intuitive interfaces, offering interactive visualizations, and providing multilingual support. Features such as screen reader compatibility, high-contrast visuals, and accessible navigation cater to diverse user needs, including those with disabilities. By reducing usability barriers, open data becomes more accessible to a wider audience, driving engagement and effective utilization.

7.2 Governance recommendations

7.2.1 Build shared goals and values by promoting shared culture

Fostering collaboration among government agencies, private sector actors, researchers, and the public necessitates the development of shared objectives and values. Organizing stakeholder consultations, workshops, and collaborative forums can help align goals and create a common vision for open data initiatives. Promoting a culture of transparency, innovation, and community-driven solutions strengthens long-term commitment to open data practices.

7.2.2 Scope local problems and build collaborative networks with local stakeholders

Addressing local challenges through open data requires conducting needs assessments and actively engaging with local stakeholders. By identifying specific problems and collaborating with communities, policymakers can develop targeted data-driven interventions. Building sustainable data-sharing networks and fostering partnerships with local organizations help ensure that open data initiatives effectively respond to regional priorities and constraints.

7.2.3 Facilitate collaboration between domain experts and open data experts

Bridging the gap between subject matter experts and data scientists enhances the quality and applicability of open data solutions. Structured initiatives such as hackathons, interdisciplinary workshops, and collaborative research projects provide opportunities for knowledge exchange. Additionally, offering incentives like grants and training programs encourages long-term engagement and fosters innovation in data-driven decision-making.

7.2.4 Empowering marginalized stakeholders for inclusive ODEs

To create a more inclusive ODE, governments should ensure that marginalized groups, such as small-scale data contributors and NGOs, have the resources and opportunities to engage meaningfully in data-sharing activities. This can be achieved by creating accessible, multilingual feedback channels, offering capacity-building programs, and incentivizing participation through training and support. By adopting collaborative governance models and fostering community-

driven data stewardship, policymakers can bridge power imbalances and ensure that the ODE is equitable and sustainable.

7.2.5 Establishing a governance framework for open data validation

A dedicated governance framework should be implemented to oversee the technical validation of open data, ensuring data consistency, reliability, and compliance with best practices. This framework should include automated validation tools, periodic audits, and collaborative stakeholder engagement to maintain high data quality standards.

7.2.6 Enabling data analysis through low-code tools and training

To enhance the accessibility of open data for non-technical users, open (government) data holders should support the development and distribution of low-code data analysis tools. These platforms will allow users with varying levels of expertise to analyse open data and generate insights. They should also provide training for educators and intermediaries on how to use these tools effectively, ensuring that a wide range of stakeholders can participate in the data-driven decision-making process. Moreover, open (government) data holders should encourage the development and distribution of data augmentation and validation tools that support various dataset types. These tools, possibly developed by intermediaries within the ODE, should be adaptable to different data types and intended uses. By enhancing data quality through these tools, governments can ensure that open data remains accurate, relevant, and usable, further improving its value to stakeholders across sectors.

8 Limitations

While we have made significant strides in designing a framework for a sustainable ODE and strategies promoting its sustainability, we discovered several limitations in this work. First, technology is constantly evolving, which has been a challenge. As we worked on designing the ODE framework over the years, new tools and methods emerged, which sometimes required to update our work or to reassess the relevancy of studied technologies. Technologies like AI and data infrastructure are rapidly evolving, and our strategies may not always keep up.

Second, multidisciplinary research played a huge role in shaping our work, but it also made things more complicated. We brought in expertise from different fields, all highly relevant to the ODE, which was great for broadening our approach. However, this also led to moments of confusion as we tried to merge different ideas, methods, and terminology. This added complexity to the research process. Furthermore, managing multidisciplinary research posed a significant challenge and introduced limitations in our work. Some of the key limitations we observed include differing terminologies and frameworks, varying research methodologies, conflicting priorities and expectations, and challenges with data compatibility and integration.

Additionally, the design and validation of our ODE framework was not a simple task. It required a delicate balance between making it flexible enough for different contexts while still providing a solid structure. The process was iterative, and as we progressed, we found ourselves refining ideas more than expected, which led to several new challenges along the way. Lastly, as we moved through the project, our understanding of key concepts like inclusiveness and circularity evolved. This shift helped us improve our approach, but it also showed how hard it is to keep a long-term project consistent when new insights keep emerging.

9 Conclusion

The main objective of this deliverable was to design an overarching sustainable ODE framework and to propose strategies to pave the way towards a user driven, circular, inclusive, and skill-based Open Data Ecosystem (ODE).

The proposed ODE framework serves as a middle step a comprehensive prototype for achieving this vision. It integrates key components such as stakeholders, data provision and usage, ODE drivers, driving forces, new concepts (e.g., AI4Data and Data4AI), incentives, values, collaboration, and infrastructure. By emphasizing continuous focus on resources, governance, and enabling environments, the framework provides a structured approach to addressing the multi-dimensional challenges of ODEs. The development of the framework also resulted in a better understanding of the concepts of inclusivity and circularity of ODE. Initially, inclusiveness was framed primarily around the inclusion of non-governmental actors as data providers, and circularity focused on non-government entities enhancing and returning open government data (OGD) back into the ecosystem. However, our findings indicate that these definitions were too narrow. Inclusiveness must also encompass equity in data access and usability—addressing issues of representation, language, and digital capacity—while integrating user driven principles such as the FAIR framework. Similarly, circularity should not be limited to improved OGD but expanded to any valuable contribution users of open data make to the ecosystem, whether through improved open datasets, tools, services, or practices.

We applied an inductive research methodology to identify key elements of ODE which were further mapped to the ODE drivers and corresponding ODE framework components so that we can make them actionable strategies tailored to particular ODE framework components and drivers. We arrived at a set of 29 strategies (section 6.1, 6.2, and 6.3 subheadings) and additional approaches after synthesizing 83 initial strategies. This resulted in eleven recommendations for institutions and actors producing, using or otherwise contributing to the ODE, to be implemented in order to support sustainable ODEs. These 11 recommendations may improve usability and accessibility, quality, and participation through a set of 5 technical and 6 governance strategies.

To sustain the ecosystem, the facilitation of open data sharing among non-government data holders is crucial. Encouraging private entities, research institutions, and civil society organizations to share data requires addressing legal, technical, and organizational barriers. Establishing clear licensing frameworks, anonymization techniques, and sustainable open data-sharing mechanisms can help build trust among non-government data holders. Open-source platforms can further support seamless collaboration by ensuring interoperability and compliance with existing data standards. Partnerships and coordination efforts should also be strengthened to promote contributions from diverse stakeholders.

In conclusion, achieving a sustainable ODE requires a multifaceted approach that balances inclusivity, circularity, user driven engagement, and skill-based empowerment. This deliverable represents a step forward in the evolution of ODEs. By addressing the gaps in current systems and leveraging the proposed strategies, the framework and strategies outlined in this study pave the way for a more inclusive, equitable, and innovative open data future. Ultimately, this work contributes to the broader goal of harnessing open data as a powerful tool for societal and economic transformation.

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Annex 1 - Open Data Ecosystem Strategies

Table 4: Strategies for user driven open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
Coordinating functions should be discharged by public administrations to bring together open data providers and open data users to openly discuss their needs.	Public administrations should routinely consult with open data users and providers from the citizenry, the private sector and the public sector to understand evolving needs of these stakeholders and undertake open data initiatives that respond to these needs. Public administrations should also provide funding to collaborative open data initiatives, which can then serve a coordinating function. At the same time, coordinating functions can also lead to open data ecosystems in unexpected ways. For instance, the UK mapping agency – Ordnance Survey – did create large geographic datasets, but many open data users were dissatisfied that these datasets were not freely distributed. This led to the birth of OpenStreetMap (see https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/History_of_OpenStreetMap) – an open platform for crowd-source geospatial data, which could be considered an example of a sustainable ODE. Future research can explore mechanisms for non-governmental actors to discharge coordinating functions.	Governance	Coordinating functions to be discharged by governmental actors. With the right incentives, such functions can be discharged by non-governmental actors as well
Partnerships should be formed between public administrations / international organisations and other civic open data user groups to co-develop open data initiatives, which can prompt contributions from other actors.	This is another tool for collaborations between public bodies and other civic actor groups. These partnerships enable other actors, like non-specialised users, to contribute to open data initiatives. These partnerships can be formal. In many cases however, NGOs initiate projects and build partnerships with government bodies on their own, which could take the form of more informal partnerships. In such cases, there should be greater willingness on the part of government bodies to engage in such partnerships with NGOs. The partnership (whether formal or informal) should also include a feedback loop, where citizen-contributed data (as in the case of CityLAB Berlin) and NGO-created data (as in the case of Femicides in Europe) are integrated into open government data initiatives.	Governance, Market, Incentives	Willingness on part of public administrations to engage in formal and informal partnerships with other civic actor groups
A strong interorganisational culture oriented towards effecting social and economic impact of open data in a participative manner is also useful.	Organisations should have a strong internal culture of contributing to as well as realising value from ODEs. This can then enable inter-organisational cultures, as well as potentially foster partnerships. These organisational cultures can also serve as motivations for actor groups to engage in open data initiatives. Such cultures can be cultivated using formal institutions like legal frameworks, together with informal approaches to creating shared understandings among the various open data actors.	Culture	Cultivating strong organisational cultures oriented towards open data
Enhancing accessibility of metadata	Metadata must remain accessible despite the unavailability of datasets, facilitating the ongoing utilization of historical context for research purposes.	Ensures that datasets remain significant and	1. Implement metadata repositories 2. Provide documentation for metadata usability

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
		valuable throughout time, hence contributing to the sustainability of the ecosystem.	
Better interfaces and feedback mechanisms for open data provision	Important to design and develop the necessary technical mechanisms including new interfaces and user interaction methods that enhance the way NGD holders are creating and sharing open data that is available, usable and valuable to a wide range of stakeholders, fostering a more inclusive and effective ODE.	Data provision, Enabling Environment, Infrastructure	Enhance the foster improved open data platforms' interface and feedback mechanisms by adopting User driven design, inclusion of diverse user groups in society and active feedback loops while making use of new technologies wherever this is possible; e.g., Natural Language Processing, Virtual and Augmented Reality, AI, and Chatbots.
User driven Feedback mechanisms	Feedback mechanisms, including dataset rating systems, dataset comments, and direct user feedback through discussion forum, are essential for enhancing data quality and ensuring user-friendly portals.	Integrates user contributions so that it can improve overall dataset relevance and usability.	Establish effective feedback mechanisms.
Identification of gaps between the needs of user groups and the current features of open data platforms with respect to user interfaces	user-interfaces are basic part of the FAIR principles when it comes to findability of open data. The Findability aspect of FAIR Data Provision is the primary focus. This principle of data discovery is acknowledged as the fundamental premise of data use. Data and metadata should be easy to find for both humans and computers.	open data infrastructure	The data should be findable to wide range of users with diverse searching options.
FAIR Principles	open data portal must be up to par of FAIR data principles for all users. It supports, FAIR principles for specialist and non-specialist open data stakeholders	open data infrastructure	The FAIR Principles should be applied to achieve the User driven ODE.
Smooth integration of open data from diverse domains	Open data publishers require a smooth data integration process to combine data from diverse sources to make a collective decision. In this way, several issues with the open data portals such as data interoperability, data transformation, data harmonization and integration of tools and technologies can be achieved.	open data infrastructure	ODE should facilitate the integration of open data from cross-domains (either government, non-government, NGOs).

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
User needs quality measures and proper profiling of the data	By providing proper data profile and quality measures of the open data can enhance its useability.	Driving Force: Data quality	Follow some kind of quality standards and data profiling techniques to achieve the user-needs regarding the data quality and usability.
Data consumers capacity building	visualization skills, training in data analytics	Value	need to build my skillset in the field of data visualisation and build capacity regarding data issues (fragmentation, aggregated data, unreliable data, and sensitive data).
Multi-format data access	provide the end-users with open data in multi-formats such as open formats, APIs, bulk downloads to tackle diverse needs	open data infrastructure	Use open standards, open formats available to engage the users with diverse needs. Some users require data in bulk, other requires APIs, and other requires Linked open data
Unified view for open data publication process	Open Data providers require a unified view of publishing dashboard. For instance, several government levels participate in open data publications, regional, decentralized, and municipal level. They should have access to unified portal to publish their datasets	open data infrastructure	Develop a standardized open data portal interface to make the data publication process easier.
Anonymization of the open dataset before publishing must be the norm	Open Data providers must have access to tools to increase the anonymity of open data before making it public.	open data infrastructure	Use/develop tools to anonymize the open data
Making available integrated datasets from diverse fields for users with diverse needs is needed	The necessity for integration of data and accessibility feasible for user groups with varying needs (e.g., visual impairment, dyslexia, and others)	open data infrastructure	Introduce tools for unified view of data and physically impaired user groups.
Portability of infrastructure in the open data domain	The portability of infrastructure will help transfer the knowledge of open data infrastructure to another organization	open data infrastructure	Seek guidance and infrastructure portals from the already developed portals from other countries, areas, regions to develop your one.
Community Portal for interaction	The data portal should provide a place where users can connect with other users in a community, based on similar interests.	Enabling Environment	Open Data community portal development helps in identification of issues with data, the possible use of data, future improvements.
Technical openness of the datasets	By opening the datasets, it technically means to follow the dataset standards, formats, and other protocols to enhance the data integration across different systems and to facilitate the	Data Provision	Adopting standards, requirements, and guidelines to open data technically.

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
	better accessibility of the open data. Technical openness contributes to the technical interoperability of open data.		
Allowing the user to upload their dataset	A user can upload an updated version of the existing dataset. In this way, other users can use cleaned, modified, augmented, or transformed datasets for specific tasks. This feature also contributes to the open data interoperability.	Data Provision	developing a pipeline to engage the other open data providers as well.
Boundary-making in relation to ODEs	To define the boundaries of an ODE, actors should be aware of the socio-technical conditions where their interactions with other actors take place. These conditions refer on one hand to social components such as historical, geographical aspects, social and cultural norms, organization norms and community affiliations, as well as practices, traditions, personal motivations and values. On the other hand, the technical aspects include soft and hard data infrastructures, interoperability practices, standards, laws and regulations. Ecosystem mapping can be done using tools from the discipline of design thinking and theoretical principles from the discipline of information visualization and communication.	ODE	Awareness is needed of the socio-technical conditions in which interactions between actors take place.
Supporting communities of ODEs	To support the formation of communities around the use of open data, actors of the ODE should be knowledgeable of the purposes and practices that can be affected by open data. Shared purposes typically revolve around public and/ or local concerns, therefore they directly affect citizens, local communities or digital communities. Communities of practice typically form when experts, practitioners and academics explore societal problems by developing knowledge, tools, practices that address those problems. Research done in the field of participatory design focuses on empowering communities of shared purpose, while disciplines such as data science and engineering, engineering design, computer science typically form communities of practice around open data.	Enabling environment	Actors should be knowledgeable of the purposes and practices that can be affected through open data.
Encouraging participation and shared decision-making	To encourage polycentricity through participation and collaborative decision making in the ODE, actors with more power such as institutions, organizations, communities that represent the status quo should ensure that those typically with less power such as citizens, students, research participants as well as less represented and disadvantaged groups are being actively encouraged to communicate their feedback, needs and concerns, as a first step. Moreover, they should be empowered to actively contribute to the creation of strategies and plans, practices and assessments, products and services. The discipline of (critical) data studies provide tools, approaches and theoretical concepts that challenge existing power structures and propose more just and equitable alternatives.	Governance	Powerful actors and organizations should ensure that less powered, less represented and disadvantaged actors and organizations are encouraged to provide feedback and even actively contribute.
Considering appropriate legal mechanisms	To encourage the use of open licenses – including open data licenses for databases, Creative Commons licenses for content, and open source software licenses for software code and other software artefacts. Licenses have been central to the creation and continuation of knowledge, information and data commons. Where the data in question does not relate to any personal or sensitive information, broad licenses should be used that impose little to no	Enabling Environment (Regulations)	Use of open licenses should be encouraged

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Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
	restriction on reuse. Further, governments should, to the extent possible and subject to security concerns, procure open-source infrastructures for open data technologies. Here, the open licenses also serve to instil a culture of communiting.		
Designing an ecology of interoperable projects	To focus on interoperability and data portability and have a broad understanding of these concepts. In particular, efforts for interoperability should encompass technical interoperability (through, for example, semantic and syntactic interoperability of open data systems/portals and through standardized formats for (open) data, as also noted in the empirical data collected) as well as generative interoperability (through adoption of policies aimed at nurturing public spaces for decision-making in relation to open data needs and challenges). Support should be provided to regulatory measures aimed at broad interoperability and portability, through advocacy and political action.	open data infrastructure	Focus should be put on - different types of - interoperability and data portability
Ensuring sustainability of ODEs	In terms of economic sustainability of ODEs, advocacy for availability of public funds can be accompanied with insights from economic and business models of digital commons/information commons/data commons projects, from collaborative peer production. Contributions to social sustainability can be ensured through the adoption of critically situated approaches to participation from critical data studies.	Enabling environment	To ensure sustainability of ODEs, different types of funding models (public funding, private funding, etc.) should be considered.
The availability of open data platform based on federated architecture.	To some extent, a federated architecture could address the current shortcomings where open data across different domains and/or jurisdictions are segmented due to multiple open data providers. The federated architecture means that users can easily integrate open data from multiple domains and/or jurisdictions based on interoperable data standards, but the maintenance of the data still falls under the responsibility of the original provider. This would be valuable to address complex global and local challenges requiring a multidisciplinary and multiscale data-based approach.	Intermediaries	Open data intermediaries could consider providing an open data platform based on federated architecture.
Soliciting various needs of existing and potential open data actors	Open data intermediaries can play a role to understand and gather the needs of existing and potential open data actors with respect to the supply, processing, and reuse of open data. Certain needs may not be immediately apparent but can be uncovered by understanding the challenges that these actors face. These needs may also not be directly visible unless there are avenues for these needs to be communicated by different actors. Open data intermediaries can provide such avenues.	Intermediaries	Open data intermediaries could play an active role in identifying and understanding various needs of open data actors. They can then help to address these needs or communicate these needs to those who may be able to address (such as data providers).

Table 5: Strategies for inclusive open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
There should be continued focus on publication of open government datasets by public administration.	To realise value out of open data, it is important that high-quality open datasets are easily available. Accordingly, public administrations should continue to release open datasets, based on legal mandates as well as on a voluntary basis. To ensure that public administrations prioritize release of open data, it may be important to evaluate different enforcement as well as incentive structures.	Enabling Environment (Regulations)	Continued implementation of legal mandates for open government data.
Shared open infrastructures for publishing and use of data and information are important, including for non-governmental data holders	Shared open infrastructures for accessing, publishing and using open data are important, as not all actors may have the resources necessary to develop such infrastructures from scratch.	Infrastructure	Public financing and maintenance of shared open infrastructures, like the European Open Science Cloud
Facilitating multi-format data access for different users	Providing datasets in multiple formats enhances accessibility for NGOs, businesses, and researchers with distinct technical skills	It encourages inclusiveness ensuring the accessibility of data is in accordance with the needs of users.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enable diverse data formats and API options 2. Build accessible user interfaces to enhance usability for non-technical users.
Addressing barriers to local community access to open data	Communities require localized, interpretable datasets accompanied by metadata to utilize data effectively for decision-making and advancements in society.	Promotes inclusivity by enabling access and utility of open data at a community level.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide tools for local data interpretation 2. Create community-specific manuals and localized data insights platforms
Open Data contribution from non-government actors	The need to escape the narrow limits of only governmental bodies being active contributors to the ODE; rather, include other stakeholders (non-governmental data groups) as potential contributors.	Enabling Environment	Analyse the barriers, motivations, and technical requirements for non-government data holder groups to share their data and propose technical mechanisms to enable/facilitate this purpose.
Alignment of interests	The framework must align organizational, societal, and individual interests to foster collaboration and shared responsibility	Collaboration, Values	Create shared goals and values among diverse stakeholders within an ODE. This ensures cohesive collaboration and maximizes the ecosystem's ability to deliver value

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			across its users, contributors, and beneficiaries.
Community-centric design	Students' motivations highlight the importance of focusing on real-world relevance and fostering their contributions.	Infrastructure	Community-centric design prioritizes the needs, preferences and involvement of communities in the ODE.
Lowering barriers to data access	Ensuring the inclusivity of open data portals involves the provision of multilingual support, user-friendly interfaces, and accessibility for non-technical users.	Promotes balanced participation and equitable opportunity by expanding the ecosystem to underrepresented groups.	Simplify interfaces with user-friendly designs and incorporate multilingual support and accessibility features.
Governance mechanisms to support bottom-up initiatives	Open data governance mechanisms should also support communities and local environment to interact and benefit of ODEs not just as users of data. Local partnerships and networks might be supported by new governance mechanisms with a bottom-up perspective	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure	Scoping at local problems and building networks of actors and open dataflow among them
Interdisciplinary collaboration	Collaboration between domain-experts and data experts. Domain-experts can contribute with contextual knowledge and priorities that need to be addressed with open data. Data experts can contribute their skills for data analysis (cleaning, visualization, etc.).	Enabling Environment	Apply strategies to incentivize and facilitate the collaboration of domain experts and data experts
Open data event design	Open data events (such as hackathons, mapathons, etc.) can contribute to increase the inclusiveness of ODEs if designed appropriately (group formation methods, agenda, activities, etc.)	Enabling Environment	Open data events should be designed to be accessible by non-specialist users.
Institutionalization of open data events	Public administration bodies can organize and financially support open data events, which provide networking and learning opportunities, especially for non-specialist users.	Enabling Environment	The public administration should institutionalize and support open data events
Comprehensive dataset coverage	Availability of a wide variety of thematic datasets such as from different domains such as from science and transport and so on	Data Provision	Adopting thematic classification of datasets from EDP or other classification such as SDGs
CARE principles account for power dynamics in ODEs.	Legal avenues for redistributing value need to recognise and account for the politics of open data production and re-use. Normatively, this can be achieved through an orientation towards 'data justice'. (Taylor, 2017) In terms of practical implementation, legal frameworks for open data initiatives could refer to CARE principles in addition to the FAIR principles for data quality management. (Di Staso et al., 2023).	ODE	In terms of practical implementation, legal frameworks for open data initiatives could refer to CARE principles in addition to the FAIR principles for data quality

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			management. (Di Staso et al., 2023). These CARE Principles do not focus only on inherent qualities of data that enable more sharing and re-use, but also focus on power differentials. As a result, CARE Principles also focus on realising collective benefit from open datasets, as well as ensuring commitment to ethics. (Carroll et al., 2020). There are examples of CARE principles being translated into the design and implementation of open data initiatives - such as the Open Data Mekong project. (Chung & Chung, 2019; DCPC, 2024).
Legal avenues for redistributing value in the ODE need to account for the current inequities in open data initiatives. 1/3	Redistributing value in the ODE must address existing inequities, as open datasets are inherently political and shaped by systemic biases. While principles like FAIR improve data quality and representativeness, they often treat datasets as neutral, ignoring critical gaps. Missing data, such as underrepresentation of Global South countries during the Covid-19 pandemic or indigenous communities in the Global North, skews decision-making and global policy. Similarly, localized examples, like Brussels' daycare data failing to integrate mobility information, highlight the practical limitations of open datasets in addressing accessibility and equity issues.	Enabling environment	The EU's Implementing Regulation on High-Value Datasets (2023/138), while fostering innovation by prioritizing economically valuable datasets, needs to be applied more equitably. Critics highlight that focusing on efficiency and market productivity marginalizes citizens' rights and participation. To address this, equitable implementation could involve expanding dataset categories to include social data, as seen in India's focus on poverty alleviation or Glasgow's project on well-being indicators, ensuring that open data serves not only economic growth but also societal needs and inclusivity.
Legal avenues for redistributing value in the ODE need to account for	Redistributing value in the ODE must address existing inequities, as open datasets are inherently political and shaped by systemic biases. While principles like FAIR improve data	Enabling environment	Legal institutions should focus on ensuring commercial actors in open

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Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
the current inequities in open data initiatives. 2/3	quality and representativeness, they often treat datasets as neutral, ignoring critical gaps. Missing data, such as underrepresentation of Global South countries during the Covid-19 pandemic or indigenous communities in the Global North, skews decision-making and global policy. Similarly, localized examples, like Brussels' daycare data failing to integrate mobility information, highlight the practical limitations of open datasets in addressing accessibility and equity issues.		data initiatives prioritize the public interest. Courts can establish guidelines for open data intermediaries, as illustrated by the ECHR ruling in Satakunnan Markkinapörssi Oy v. Finland, which restricted companies from misusing publicly accessible tax data for sensationalism instead of fostering meaningful public debate. Additionally, public procurement frameworks can be adapted to require private service providers to share data generated during public service delivery in open, machine-readable formats. Barcelona's use of "data sovereignty clauses" in procurement contracts offers a strong model for balancing commercial involvement with public accountability.
Legal avenues for redistributing value in the ODE need to account for the current inequities in open data initiatives. 3/3	Redistributing value in the ODE must address existing inequities, as open datasets are inherently political and shaped by systemic biases. While principles like FAIR improve data quality and representativeness, they often treat datasets as neutral, ignoring critical gaps. Missing data, such as underrepresentation of Global South countries during the Covid-19 pandemic or indigenous communities in the Global North, skews decision-making and global policy. Similarly, localized examples, like Brussels' daycare data failing to integrate mobility information, highlight the practical limitations of open datasets in addressing accessibility and equity issues.	Enabling environment	Private law instruments, such as open licenses, can promote equitable value creation in the ODE by addressing power imbalances and fostering ethical data sharing. While open licenses like Creative Commons and Open Database Licenses were originally designed to counter copyright restrictions and encourage re-use, new challenges like data privacy, competition, and data colonialism necessitate their reimagining. For example, the University of Pretoria's Data Science Law Lab has developed a data

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Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			license for African language datasets, requiring stronger share-alike obligations from re-users in developed countries, ensuring value flows back to the Global South and countering data extractivism.
The availability of open data platform for non-government open data provision and reuse	The availability of open data platform for non-government open data provision and reuse may stimulate open data sharing through the availability of appropriate technical tools, alignment of private value and interests with open data sharing, availability of resources (financial, time, people/workforce), and the existence of data sharing communities.	Open data infrastructure	Establish a national or supra-national consortium for open data sharing by non-public organizations. Among other things, this consortium could develop and maintain non-proprietary technical infrastructure for open data sharing. The consortium may be governed by a committee composed of public, private, and civil sector stakeholders that facilitate collective decision-making on various technical and non-technical aspects. The consortium and its infrastructure may be supported by joint multi-stakeholder financial cooperation based on agreed terms.

Table 6: Strategies for circular open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
Partnerships should be formed between public administrations / international organisations and other civic open data user groups to co-develop open data initiatives, which can prompt contributions from other actors.	This is another tool for collaborations between public bodies and other civic actor groups. These partnerships enable other actors, like non-specialised users, to contribute to open data initiatives. The partnership (whether formal or informal) should also include a feedback loop, where citizen-contributed data (as in the case of CityLAB Berlin) and NGO-created data (as in the case of Femicides in Europe) are integrated into open government data initiatives.	Governance, Market, Incentives	Partnerships can encourage non-government data holders to contribute open data, in addition to being users of open data.
Motivations of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified.	Enabling Environment	Key enablers to contribute data to the ODE were identified, that relate to the motivations and barriers found by users.
Enhancing interoperability through open standards and metadata	Ensuring technical openness in datasets through interoperable standards improves system integration and enhances usability	Strengthens the ecosystem by enabling seamless integration of datasets across sectors and platforms.	1. Adopt open standards for datasets 2. Implement metadata validation tools for consistent data quality
Promoting reusable dataset integration techniques	Techniques like data blending and augmentation improve the ecosystem's efficiency and user engagement	Encourages data reuse and value creation in the ecosystem	1. Provide training on dataset linking and blending tools 2. Enable version control for community-shared datasets.
Incentivising open data sharing by open data holders in ODE through governance strategies	An approach to steer the behaviour of non-government data holders towards open data through a governance strategy.	A governance strategy options to incentives open data provision by infomediaries with other actors in the ODE in the future.	1. Promote training to improve technical skills for NGOs that lack them. 2. Creating NGOs' common platform for open data sharing. 3. Financial resources are often scarce, so to support NGOs' projects long-term, more financial cooperation

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			is needed. 4. Promote training to improve open data awareness for NGOs that lack it.
Value (co-)creation by the ODE actors	Understanding potential contributions of open government data users to the ODE	As-is state of contributions by infomediaries to the ODI towards value creation from open data	NGOs' current and potential contributions can be in the form of different values that constitute social use values, as these organisations cover a wide range of activities and exist as intermediaries rather than in end-user or producer only form. They are helping the users and the data provided by collaborating and addressing both of them and by adding value through these collaborations.
Enhanced data creation process (for NGD holders and beyond) through better quality, integration and validation tools	Important to improve and simplify the data creation process for NGD holders incorporating solutions and tools for the creation of better-quality data (including metadata), as well as integration and validation tools and techniques complying to the requested standards.	Data provision, AI4Data, Enabling Environment, Infrastructure	Enhance the data creation process by employing several technical mechanisms and technologies to improve critical aspects of data creation, quality and integration, such as augmenting semantic interoperability with the help of Large Language Models to automate or semi-automate processes that improve it, improving metadata annotation in open data portals using AI, or validating/checking technical compliance of data on the Web.
Enhanced data sharing through better licensing and anonymisation	Important to develop new technical mechanisms and solutions towards the creation of anonymised datasets in an automated way, as well as the creation of clear legal frameworks and licensing policies that are acceptable to a diverse range of stakeholders, fostering a trustworthy environment for open data exchange.	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure	Enhance data's licensing and anonymisation by employing technological facilitators to achieve this purpose, such as Machine

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			Learning, Data encryption, GenAI and legal interoperability facilitators.
Boundary objects	The concept of shared tools or platforms as "boundary objects" facilitates communication and collaboration across diverse user communities.	Infrastructure	Boundary objects are essential for fostering inclusivity, enhancing collaboration, and bridging gaps between stakeholders such as governments, NGOs, businesses, and individual citizens.
Technical and contextual support	ODEs should bridge the technical and contextual knowledge gap needed to extract value from data at different stages of its lifecycle	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure	Design open data infrastructures as hubs for creativity, learning, exploration, and knowledge sharing
Dynamic roles and interactions	In circular ecosystems, actors might adopt different roles such as user, providers or intermediaries according to their potential contributions. Interactions are dynamic as well as their role	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure	Focus on value creation and potential contributions showing a rich network of roles and interactions
Networks and layers	The dynamics and interconnected interactions in ODEs might be represented as networks. A multi-layer perspective might contribute to represent different value generation and stakeholders perspectives such as business, government and local communities	Enabling Environment, Data Usage, Infrastructure	Visualise ODEs as multi-layer networks mapping
Open Data accessibility and interoperability	The Open Data Platform (ODP) requires backing for data integration and interoperability from a range of stakeholders, including governmental and non-governmental entities.	— Resources — open data infrastructure — Data Provider	Employing open data standards and formats can streamline data accessibility and sharing within ODEs, enhancing their circularity.
Comprehensive dataset coverage	Availability of a wide variety of thematic datasets such as from different domains such as from science and transport and so on	Data Provision	Adopting thematic classification of datasets from EDP or other classification such as SDGs
Scalability and performance of the portal	the open data volume, variety and velocity increases by the time, so open data portals should be scalable, and performance should be high to accommodate these variations over the time.	— Resources — open data infrastructure — Data Provider	Follow the big data and cloud computing technologies to make the portal more scalable and improve performance
User-friendly interfaces	Establish an easy-to-navigate interface for the datasets and analysis tools that anyone can understand and use.	open data infrastructure	Facilitate better data exploration and comprehension by including interactive visualisation tools.

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
<p>The financial value created or captured by actors depend on the roles they play in the ODE, as they can play multiple roles at the same time. 1/6</p>	<p>Actors in an ODE (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organisations, and citizens) are not wedded to any particular role. In other words, they can play multiple roles at the same time or different roles in different contexts.</p>	<p>ODE</p>	<p>Commitments to provide continuous and adequate funding for maintaining and developing open data infrastructure and support ought to be institutionalized, for example, through supranational, national, or local laws. Conversely, open data has to be considered as an infrastructure (like roads, clean water, etc.) and be accounted for in the tax policy design that, at the same time, does not disincentivize companies from continue using open data.</p>
<p>The financial value created or captured by actors depend on the roles they play in the ODE, as they can play multiple roles at the same time. 2/6</p>	<p>Actors in an ODE (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organisations, and citizens) are not wedded to any particular role. In other words, they can play multiple roles at the same time or different roles in different contexts and these roles influence the types of financial value they can create or capture.</p>	<p>ODE</p>	<p>Some restructuring, streamlining, and coordination of open data management and provision may be necessary within and across government agencies to save (transaction) costs as open data providers further. At the same time, it may also be worth coordinating with other agencies that are not necessarily open data providers to implement contractual obligations with third-party vendors that collect data through their government-funded projects/undertakings to give such data to the government free of charge (including augmented data on top of initially government open data), so that (some of) the data can then be provided as open data. This saves the government from (re)collecting the data.</p>

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
The financial value created or captured by actors depend on the roles they play in the ODE, as they can play multiple roles at the same time. 3/6	Actors in an ODE (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organisations, and citizens) are not wedded to any particular role . In other words, they can play multiple roles at the same time or different roles in different contexts and these roles influence the types of financial value they can create or capture.	ODE	One possible way to recuperate some of the costs of providing open data is for government agencies to also provide value-added services based on open data at fees. This involves revisiting, clarifying, and potentially amending existing laws related to government-market roles and competition.
The financial value created or captured by actors depend on the roles they play in the ODE, as they can play multiple roles at the same time. 4/6	Actors in an ODE (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organisations, and citizens) are not wedded to any particular role . In other words, they can play multiple roles at the same time or different roles in different contexts and these roles influence the types of financial value they can create or capture.	ODE	Government agencies should be obligated to use open data whenever it is available and to inform open data providers of any errors in the data. This saves costs for them as open data users as well as to open data providers in ensuring data quality.
The financial value created or captured by actors depend on the roles they play in the ODE, as they can play multiple roles at the same time. 5/6	Actors in an ODE (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organisations, and citizens) are not wedded to any particular role. In other words, they can play multiple roles at the same time or different roles in different contexts and these roles influence the types of financial value they can create or capture.	ODE	Tax incentives may be worth considering enticing companies and citizens to contribute to open data initiatives as funders or data providers. The case of the Wikimedia Foundation and OpenStreetMap Foundation being granted tax-deductible status in some countries, where companies and citizens who donate to these organizations can claim tax deductions, is a good example to consider for other open data initiatives.
The financial value created or captured by actors depend on the roles they play in the ODE, as they can play multiple roles at the same time. 6/6	Actors in an ODE (e.g., government agencies, companies, non-profit organisations, and citizens) are not wedded to any particular role. In other words, they can play multiple roles at the same time or different roles in different contexts and these roles influence the types of financial value they can create or capture.	ODE	Governments should recognize that they are no longer the only open data providers. Hence, they should consider supporting citizen-generated or crowdsourced open data projects, such as

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Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			OpenStreetMap, by financially supporting or contributing their own data to these projects. At the same time, governments can also leverage open data from these projects as one of their data sources. This may lead to more cost-sharing in open data initiatives within the ecosystem.
In ODEs, value is seen as multifaceted and dependent on the dynamics of user engagement, circularity, inclusivity, and skill-based development within open data systems	The complexity of 'valuing' open data arises from the various stages in the open data usage process, which range from collection and storage to analysis and sharing. Each stage presents unique requirements and risks that need to be managed to maintain the data's utility and integrity while ensuring responsible data practices that consider privacy, equity, and accountability (S. G. Verhulst, 2021). In the ODEs proposal, the concept of value is approached from a broader, ecosystem-oriented perspective rather than merely traditional use-value.	ODE	A purpose-driven approach, rather than a User driven one, can enhance ODEs to better reflect the understanding of social value. Purpose-directed models establish clear goals, usually concentrating on encouraging responsible data usage while advancing societal benefits, such as improved healthcare and environmental sustainability.
Various open data intermediation value propositions addressing various real-world challenges and providing innovative solutions	Greater awareness and inspiration on the potential value-added services based that can be offered based on open data should be promoted across various sectors/domains to encourage the emergence of more open data intermediaries that help address real-world challenges.	Intermediaries	Open data advocates (such as open data NGOs, researchers, and public agencies) could engage with domain-specific industry players (such as mobility, agriculture, energy sectors) to showcase the potential use of open data and exemplary value-added services.
Advisory, consultancy or support services to existing or potential open data actors	Some existing or potential open data actors may require additional various forms of support and knowledge to supply, process, or reuse open data.	Intermediaries	Open data intermediaries (within or outside public sector) should consider introducing functions to provide technical and non-technical supports to other open data actors in supplying, processing, and reusing open data.
Initiating engagement and interaction among open data actors	Some potential collaborations between open data actors may happen with the help of open data intermediaries that bring different actors together or initiate possible connection or engagement.	Intermediaries	Beyond holding events such as hackathons or conferences that bring various actors in one place to

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Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
			connect, open data intermediaries may also consider initiating or leading collaborative initiatives that harness the resources and expertise of multiple open data actors.
The availability of open-source software for open data supply, processing, and reuse	Certain open data actors may face financial constraints to purchase or subscribe proprietary software to supply, process, or reuse open data. Hence, the availability of open-source software may alleviate such constraints.	Intermediaries	The development of open-source software should be supported, especially by providing funds for open-source software development and maintenance.
Sustainable business models for open data intermediaries	Open data intermediaries require sustainable business models to ensure its longevity and performance.	Intermediaries	Incubator or similar programs to support the design and development of open data intermediaries' business models could be initiated to help existing and future open data intermediaries. These programs could be catered not only to for-profit but also non-profit open data intermediaries, as the former also requires sustainable business models.
Fiscal incentives in exchange for contributions to open data initiatives	Open data initiatives carried out by non-profit entities such as Wikimedia and OpenStreetMap require sustained funding. The same goes to open-source software initiatives that enable the processing and use of open data. Citizens and companies could be given fiscal incentives (such as tax discounts) in exchange for their contribution to these open data/open-source initiatives, either in monetary or data/content form.	Resources	Governments should consider offering financial incentives to citizens and companies that support open data or open-source projects.
Enabler: Availability of training in data skills and literacy	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From the barrier "Lack of data skills and literacy", the enabler "Availability of training in data skills and literacy" was identified.	Incentives	By making training in data skills and literacy available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged
Enabler: Availability of appropriate technical tools	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From the motivation "To improve technical skills or internal data processes" and the barrier "Lack of technical tools", the enabler "Availability of appropriate technical tools" was identified.	Incentives	By making appropriate technical tools available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged
Enabler: Alignment of private value and interests with open data sharing	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From	Incentives	By aligning private value and interests with open data sharing,

D5.3 Strategies towards sustainable open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
	the motivation "Private value" and the barrier "Misaligned goals and interests", the enabler "Alignment of private value and interests with open data sharing" was identified.		data contribution can be enabled/leveraged
Enabler: Availability of resources (financial, time, people/workforce)	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From the barrier "Lack of resources", the enabler "Availability of resources" was identified.	Incentives	By making resources (financial, time, people/workforce) available, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged
Enabler: Existence of data-sharing communities	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From the motivations "Supporting other stakeholders", "Supporting communities" and "Belonging", the enabler "Existence of data-sharing communities" was identified.	Incentives	By making data-sharing communities exist, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged
Enabler: Awareness about the social impact of open data sharing	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From the motivation "Creating social impact" and the barrier "Lack of awareness", the enabler "Awareness about the social impact of open data sharing" was identified.	Incentives	By making stakeholders aware about the social impact of open data sharing, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged
Enabler: Presence of engagement or enjoyment activities	The motivations and barriers of non-government actors to become active contributors to the ODE were found. From these motivations and barriers, 7 key enablers were identified. From the motivation "Engagement / enjoyment", the enabler "Presence of engagement or enjoyment activities" was identified.	Incentives	By having engagement or enjoyment activities, data contribution can be enabled/leveraged

Table 7: Strategies for skill-based open data ecosystems

Key element	Description of key-element	Connection with ecosystem framework	Proposed strategy/recommendation
Providing assistance to data intermediaries to improve the quality of data	The use of methods/approaches that increase data quality, such as validation and augmentation, is crucial in order to make open datasets better and to ensure that they are accessible to all different kinds of users simultaneously.	Intermediaries are given the capacity to increase the utility of data while also developing trust and reliability within the ecosystem.	"1. Create and distribute data augmentation tools adaptable to different dataset types
Developing low-code tools for educators and data intermediaries	Low-code platforms enable teachers and intermediaries to process, analyse, and extract insights without advanced technical expertise, empowering broader participation in the ODE.	2. The tools should be capable of supporting a wide variety of data types and intended uses."	